

Energy-efficient AI-ready Data Spaces

D2.1: Data Management infrastructure and tools to support Dynamic Ecosystems

Abstract:

Deliverable D2.1 provides a detailed description of the different environments, tools and services that will ensure a well-defined and efficient management of the data infrastructure required to manage information as well as the exchange of data between tools and platforms. The main environments identified by the Reference Architecture are:

1. Data providers represented by the data management services available at the pilot sites.
2. Data Orchestration as an intermediary step that manages data sets transformation.
3. GREEN.DAT.AI as a common data infrastructures and governance frameworks to facilitates data pooling, access and [1].
4. Service Producers, similar than Data Providers, use the data once transformed by the producer's orchestration services.

Using the GREEN.DAT.AI Data Space (DS) will ensure decentralization, sovereignty, neutrality, traceability, interoperability, and findability of the data with robust identity management services[2].

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AISBL	<i>French: Association Sans But Lucrative (non-profit association)</i>
API	Application Programming Interface
AVT	Advanced Visualisation Toolkit
BDA	Big Data Analytics
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
CA	Consortium Agreement
CA	Client Application
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DAPS	Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service
DS	Data Space
DSBA	Data Space Business Alliance
DX.Y	Deliverable of WP X with number Y
EDC	Eclipse Dataspace Components
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EV	Electric Vehicles
FL	Federated Learning
GA	Grant Agreement
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IDS	International Data Spaces
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MFA	Multi-Factor Authentication
ML	Machine Learning
NGSI-LD	Next Generation Service Interface with Linked Data
NIC	Network Interface Card
NIDS	Network Intrusion Detection System
OS	Operating System
RA	Reference Architecture
RAM	Random-Access Memory
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
REST	Representational State Transfer
SSO	Single Sign-On
TA	Trusted Application
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TEE	Trusted Execution Environments
TLS	Transport Layer Security
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UC	Use Case
UI	User Interface
USB	Universal Serial Bus

Acronym	Description
WME	Workflow Management Engine
WP	Work Package
XAI	eXplainable Artificial Intelligence

Executive Summary

A data ecosystem is essential for a well-defined and efficient management of the data infrastructure required to store and process information as well as manage on-demand and near-to real-time data exchange between tools and platforms.

The GREEN.DAT.AI project data ecosystem has been designed and developed based on various elements (people, hardware, and software) that interact to produce, manage, store, organise, analyse, and share data. To facilitate a well-structured and ease-to-manage data flow between the data producer and the data/service consumer the following data environments were defined:

- Local databases that provide the data to be ingested, harmonised and stored at.
- Producer orchestration services using tools and services ensuring proper utilisation within the Data Space.
- GREEN.DAT.AI Data Space using the Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC) connector to publish available data and share data with other connectors.
- Data/service consumer orchestration services for receiving and integrating data into local databases and processing infrastructure.

While both orchestration environments are very similar, the Producer prepares data to be published in the data space, while the Data/service consumer manages the received data locally.

To facilitate and ensure seamless bi-directional data flow between the local databases and the orchestration service environment, use case (UC)-specific tools for data visualisation and additional interfaces were developed and validated.

Furthermore, tools for data management (control, analysis, and flow) between the local databases and the orchestration services were customised, deployed, and tested (StreamHandler and Workflow Management Engine), complemented by the deployment of security management tools to safeguard data flow, including Intrusion Detection and Data and Execution protection.

GREEN.DAT.AI Data Space (DS) tools and services ensure decentralisation, sovereignty, neutrality, traceability, interoperability, and findability of the data while ensuring privacy and security with robust identity management services[2].

Consequently, this deliverable outlines the environments (Orchestration and Data Space), detailing the tools, and the services used in each of them, to support the data management infrastructure crucial for GREEN.DAT.AI project's Use Cases.

1. Introduction

Data infrastructure encompasses the tools and services that form the foundation for an organisation to create, manage, use, and secure its data. Its primary role is to ensure that the accurate data reaches the right users or systems at the right time to facilitate effective, data-driven decisions. To achieve this goal, a robust data infrastructure strategy is essential for maintaining data flows, protecting data quality, minimising redundancy, and preventing crucial data from being isolated into silos[3].

A data ecosystem is crucial for managing the data infrastructure required to store, processes and exchange information on-demand and near-to real-time between tools and platforms.

The design and development of the GREEN.DAT.AI project Data ecosystem has considered the various elements (people, hardware, and software) which interactions leads to produce, manage, store, organize, analyse, and share data.

Given the need for data exchanging across different environments, GREEN.DAT.AI's data space components provide a centralised, secure, and private transportation of data between environments. These environments are:

1. **Data providers:** represented by the data management services available at the use cases and supporting the UCs requirements of data.
2. **Data Orchestration:** as an intermediary step to provide and/or obtain transformed datasets that meet data space requirements.
3. **GREEN.DAT.AI DS:** including mandatory components as a common data infrastructure and governance frameworks to facilitate data pooling, access and sharing[3].
4. **Service Producers:** to receive data from the DS and store it on their orchestration services, ensuring data transformation before being consumed by local data services.

Using the GREEN.DAT.AI DS ensures decentralisation, sovereignty, neutrality, traceability, interoperability, and findability of the data while ensures privacy and security with robust identity management services[2].

Figure 1 provides a graphic vision of the objectives achieved (final blueprint) taking as a starting point **Figure 2** (initial blueprint). Now the StreamHandler and the Workflow Management Engine controls the tools and services required for harmonisation, storage, processing, reporting and visualisation of data, all integrated around the orchestration services and connected with local data bases, and for data ingestion, the tools deployed are related to the environment in which they will be used - Kafka and local (custom) connectors - and for Data Space service the Sovity connector (based on an EDC connector).

The Energy Efficiency Testing Framework has been included as an analytic service and it ingests data from the orchestration services or local data bases. Visualisation tools have been designed, developed, tested, and deployed at pilot sites based on their use case requirements. Security aspects related to data, tools and orchestration services use are managed using KrakenD, IoT Trust-based IDs and Data & Execution protection.

Orchestration services environment and related infrastructure used as an intermediary step to enable and facilitate data management between local data bases and GREEN.DAT.AI data space or the analytic services.

Final vision Blueprint for a specific data platform (to be deployed in pilots)

Figure 1. Final vision of the blueprint of tools and services to be deployed.

1.1. Purpose of the document

GREEN.DAT.AI GA Component Title	GREEN.DAT.AI GA Component Outline	Respective Document Section(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D2.1 - Data Management infrastructure and tools to support Dynamic Ecosystems	<p>D2.1 showcases the design and development of the BDA infrastructure including the Federated Data Sovereignty services and the plan for data pipelines management and continuous integration. It also delivers the visualisation tools needed for the pilots, the workflow management engine required to schedule distributed analytics pipelines, and, finally, wrappers that secure computations & sensitive data at the edge/fog/cloud.</p> <p>A report will detail or the platform components, their interfaces, and data pipelines management mechanisms. The deliverable will include the first prototype of the visualisation workbench, interfaces, distributed analytics services, workflow management engine, and the wrappers for Securing Computations and Sensitive Data at the Edge/ Fog/Cloud.</p>	Sections 2 to 7	<p>Describe in detail both environments for data processing and exchange, as well as the tools and services available in each environment to guarantee the transfer of data required by end users, models, and services.</p> <p>The environments defined for data ingestion, harmonisation, processing, and storage are the service orchestration environment and the data space. The first is used for the transformation and storage of data from local databases until its publication in the Data Space. The second is the Data Space itself that publishes the data and enables share it between EDC connectors. Both environments require specific tools and services</p>

			<p>that have been installed and adapted to the needs of the use cases.</p> <p>For orchestration services, tools and services are used to manage the flow of data securely and efficiently both from the local databases to the DS (provider) and from the DS back to the local databases (consumer).</p> <p>For the data space, these tools and services have the purpose of controlling and monitoring data access and exchange.</p>
TASKS			
<p>Task 2.1 Big Data Analytics (BDA) Infrastructure and Federated Data Sovereignty Services for AI ready Data Spaces</p>	<p>The main objective is to design and implement a platform that enables and orchestrate Big Data Analytics over infrastructures covering all elements of computing continuum. It will include functionalities for data integration, harmonisation, storage, and processing based on FIWARE Generic Enablers, CEF building blocks and open-source technologies (e.g., Apache Software, Databricks). Specific services will be implemented for standard, secure and sovereign data sharing, including tools for ensuring interoperability and interfaces for uploading/publishing and consuming data, for achieving transparent trust through federated identifies, and for data governance covering data provenance certification, data lifecycle (including retirement) and more importantly, data usage (through policies). Connectors and interfaces will be defined with the rest of components of GREEN.DAT.AI platform.</p>	<p>Sections 2 and 3</p>	<p>To enable local data sources (data provider) to exchange information securely and efficiently with other clients (consumers or service providers), this section describes the development and implementation of a Data Space environment and its mandatory components based on the standards and directives defined for Data Spaces by both IDSA and Gaia-X. The development, testing and validation of an EDC connector and all the documentation for its implementation by the pilots is available on the project's GitHub.</p> <p>Likewise, the transversal components required for the DS to be IDSA and GAIA-X compliant have been developed and are available in the DS environment. These components include a DAPS server for Identity Management, the</p>

			Compliance module for managing agreements between DS partners, and the catalogue module to enable searching of available data.
Task 2.2 Visualisation workbench and Interfaces	This task will support the visualisation and monitoring needs of the pilot applications, by adapting AEGIS visualisation tools via different and flexibly customised widgets, schemas etc. along with the outcome of any AI/ML components per use case. The framework that will be designed as part of this task will include multi-purpose and interactive interfaces, which will fulfil the different needs of both expert and non-expert end-users according to the nature of the domain, the services designed in WP2, the specified data models & technologies developed in WP3, and the environment requirements.	Section 4	This section reports the development of the visualisation workbench and interface framework. This progress is justified by showcasing the adaptation of AEGIS visualisation tool to include flexible and customisable widgets and schemas. Additionally, the integration of AI/ML components enhances data analytics and predictive capabilities. The design of multi-purpose, interactive interfaces cater to both expert and non-expert users, ensuring the tool meet the diverse needs of various UCs within the project. These advancements collectively support the visualisation and monitoring requirements of the pilot applications.
Task 2.3 Distributed Analytics Services & Workflow Management Engine	This task will deploy a workflow engine for the orchestration of large-scale distributed analytics pipelines, building on Stream handler platform (big data real-time fault tolerant stream handler platform). The workflow engine will support the definition of complex workflows and the automated orchestration of analytics services. A multi-platform aware scheduler and registry will be developed to collect information about the different infrastructural resources and utilise them during the execution of a data analytics task over distributed data sources. The scheduler will consume high-level analytics descriptions and translate them into abstract dataflows that depict the	Section 5	This section outlines the development of a Workflow Management Engine (WME) to orchestrate pilot pipelines incorporating ML services (WP3) and WP2 components, enabling large-scale distributed analytics scenarios. Additionally, this section described the creation of a StreamHandler platform tailored to the supported scenarios and workflows, ensuring effective messaging and communication within the Data Orchestration layer of

	necessary execution flow. Therefore, the execution of pipelines will be streamlined through the semi-automatic orchestration of distributed execution engines and the utilisation of rich data sets residing in federated computing infrastructures.		the GREEN.DAT.AI Reference Architecture.
Task 2.4 Wrappers for Securing Computations and Sensitive Data at the Edge/Fog /Cloud TSI	Task 2.4 will provide a TEE continuum from edge nodes all the way to cloud in order to protect the execution of sensitive computations and the storage and transmission of data. It will employ TUC's Trust-based IDS to exclude malfunctioning or compromised nodes from polluting Federated Learning procedures or compromised IoT nodes. This will provide security, trust, and privacy in the IoT device itself. Moreover, trusted execution environments (such as Intel SGX and ARM TrustZone) which can enable remote attestation and further provide full memory encryption will be used in the pilot cases according to the existing infrastructure. These environments contain secure elements that lie in the hardware chip and support advanced cryptographic functions and physically protected storage of private and secret keys, allowing the building of a multi-layer architecture that ensures the integrity of the code and the data at runtime and prevents any data leaks from unauthorized or unwanted access. Finally, secure communication channels between the devices of each layer will be established using state-of-the-art encryption techniques prior to data transmission, ensuring the confidentiality and integrity of data in transit.	Section 6	In this section, the tools to ensure the security, confidentiality and trustworthiness of data and devices across the different layers of the GREEN.DAT.AI system, are described.
Task 2.5 Testing tool for measuring the energy efficiency of AI Services	This task will develop the common testing framework for the pilots designed in T1.4. The framework will ensure that results are measurable and comparable and aligned with the specific objectives of the project. The core of the framework will follow a black-box approach, allowing the collection of metrics for analysis for several AI/ML algorithms in several dimensions, namely: energy expenditure, data volume, time, and specific metrics according to the classes of the AI/ML	Section 7	This task details the specification of the testing tool to assess the energy performance of AI models. It includes the modules, sequence diagrams, and requirements for the three key stages of the evaluation workflow: boot, train and inference. It also details the underlying technologies

	<p>algorithms available in the project. Moreover, the framework will configure and orchestrate tests to streamline the use of the tool, including visualization of test results. The tool will be deployed by owners/developers of the algorithms/models to assess the performance of the implementation.</p>	<p>that support the individual components of the tool.</p>
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1.2. Relationship to other Deliverables

The main source of information used to develop, configure, and make available the tools and services required by both the Data Space environment and the pilots has been the deliverable D1.1 - Use Case Requirements, KPIs & Reference Architecture (RA); additional sources are detailed in D3.1 - First Version of Energy-Efficient Large- Scale Data Analytics Services and D4.7 - Pilots' Scoping Document. All technical partners supported the definition and development of the RA by attending and actively contributing during the periodic WP1 meetings.

Due to the needs of design, interoperability, and alignment of the use UCs with the availability of tools and services, periodic meetings were held in both WP2 and WP3 with all technical partners to define concepts, clarify doubts and agree on procedures. This capability for continuous exchange of information will be relevant contributions to WP3 and WP4 deliverables in the future.

Finally, the report of the results for Task T2.6 - Integration of Demonstration Services will be detailed in D2.2 - Integrated BDA Services supporting the Pilot Applications in December 2024 (M24).

1.3. Contribution to WP2 and Project Objectives

As detailed in GREEN.DAT.AI Grant Agreement, WP2 purpose *“is the implementation of the underlying infrastructure and tools required to support energy efficient and decentralised large-scale AI-ready data spaces, including the following objectives:*

- 1. to design and implement the Big Data Analytics infrastructure and the Federated Data Sovereignty services that will enable the creation of WP3 AI components.*
- 2. to develop flexible visualisation tools to facilitate the analysis, understanding and exploration of data and outcomes of AI/ML services.*
- 3. to develop powerful data analytics tools and a workflow management engine that can be executed over the highly decentralised infrastructure that characterize the new generation of computing continuum architectures including powerful edge computing devices.*
- 4. to improve the security of the computations and the confidentiality of the data through Trusted Execution Environments.*
- 5. to provide an integrated platform that will support the employment of WP3 services and their demonstration in WP4 pilots.”*

This document is the demonstration of having completed almost all the objectives set. The reason why some objectives have not yet been fully finished is because the tasks related to them have not yet been completed. This is the case of objective 5, where even though the integrated platform as well as the required tools and services are already available, supporting its use by WP3 is in the process of being consolidated to ensure its demonstration in the WP4 pilots.

1.4. Document Structure

To facilitate the understanding and location of the information provided by this document, this section provides a summary of the different chapters that construct the deliverable. Section 1: Introduction, provides an overview of the document including propose, relation with other deliverables and contributions to GREEN.DAT.AI objectives.

Section 2: Big Data Analysis (BDA) infrastructure blueprint design, details the alignment of the GREEN.DAT.AI DS and components with the RA and their alignment with GAIA-X and IDSA frameworks. The section also includes the activities performed to align the DS with the requirements for data management and exchange by pilot sites.

Section 3: Data ingestion, harmonisation, storage, and processing services, describes the tools and services used to manage the data flow through the environments available in GREEN.DAT.AI: Local data bases, Orchestration services instance and Data Space.

Section 4: Data visualisation workbench and interfaces, is focused on detailing the tools and services deployed and tested for management of interfaces and visualisation workbench at pilot sites.

Section 5: Distributed analytics services and workflow management, describes the tools and services deployed at local data bases and orchestration service instance to manage the data flow to be published and/or provided by the DS.

Section 6: Wrappers for Securing Computations and Sensitive Data at the Edge/Fog/Cloud, describes the tools that are responsible for ensuring the security, trustworthiness, and confidentiality of devices and data that exist within the GREEN.DAT.AI ecosystem.

Section 7: Energy Efficiency Testing Framework, details tools, services, and infrastructure available to process data related to efficient use of energy during the processing of data in the GREEN.DAT.AI environments.

Section 8: Conclusion and next steps, concludes the document by summarising the most relevant results related to the deliverable and provides an overview of the final steps to be performed in WP2 to ensure the completion of its objectives.

2. Big Data Analysis (BDA) infrastructure blueprint design

An initial vision of the infrastructure was the starting point for the BDA infrastructure in the form of blueprint (as common plan for the building of the environments) for the specific platforms that would be deployed at GREEN.DAT.AI pilot sites to support their use cases. **Figure 2**, GREEN.DAT.AI’s blueprint details the different aspects (ingestion, harmonisation, etc.) to be covered by the tools and service available for the different environments:

1. Local data bases to Orchestration services instances and back (bidirectional).
2. Orchestration services to Data Space using the IDSA connector for data sharing and back (bidirectional).

Both environments include security components, wrappers for security and Sensitive data at local data bases and Orchestration services instances; and a "Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service" (DAPS) for the Data Space to manage enriched identities of organisations and connectors.

Initial vision Blueprint for a specific data platform (to be deployed in pilots)

Figure 2. Initial vision of the blueprint of tools and services to be deployed.

Upon going through various evolution stages, the GREEN.DAT.AI consortium agreed on a RA that covers the scenario envisioned, where service and data providers have the chance to make their Open Data sources interact with a Data Spaces which in turn provides a set of common services they can benefit from. **Figure 3** summarises this approach and the relations of each of the involved components.

D2.1: Data Management infrastructure and tools to support Dynamic Ecosystems

Figure 3. GREEN.DAT.AI updated reference architecture.

The RA details 3 different instances of processing:

1. Service consumer/Data provider which has local data bases and data set to be shared with Service Producer via the Data Space.
 - a. Before data is exchanged, the Data Orchestration services environment transforms the local data and homogenise it based of the data rules used for data exchange by the connector.
2. Data Space environment, which can only be accessed using the EDC connector, that contains components to ensure an efficient, secure, and transparent exchange of data between the producer and the consumer.
3. Service Producer (data consumer) must also access the DS using their connector to receive the data to be used to produce added value services.
 - a. Before data can be ingested by the services and tools, the data will be processes by the local Data Orchestration services and transformed to be stored at local data bases.

Figure 4 provides additional details to the DS Common Services shown in **Figure 3** to clarify to process flow and the management processes involved in the DS functionalities.

The only contact point to entry the DS is the EDC connector which continuously can interact with the horizontal modules to manage identity, security, and compliance services.

Figure 4. GREEN.DAT.AI infrastructure for Data Space

2.1 Alignment with GREEN.DAT.AI reference architecture

Since September 2021, the Data Space initiatives[3] have become part of the Data Space Business Alliance (DSBA)[4], which includes several key organisations such as GAIA-X European Association for Data[5] and Cloud AISBL[6], the Big Data Value Association (BDVA)[7], FIWARE Foundation[8], and the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA)[9]. Collectively, these entities represent over 1,000 leading figures from the industry, including associations, research groups, innovators, and policymakers globally.

Leveraging their diverse industry expertise, resources, and knowledge, the Alliance works to increase awareness, promote technology, establish standards, and facilitate cross-industry collaboration. The primary objective of the DSBA is to establish a unified perspective on data spaces, including a shared technical framework that aligns with the partners' work and the technical compatibility among its members, which includes BDVA/DAIRO, FIWARE Foundation, GAIA-X, and IDSA. The DSBA's primary reference document, titled "Technical Convergence" version 1.0.1[10], was released in 2022-09-26.

Meanwhile, GAIA-X is focused on developing a federated open data infrastructure grounded in European principles concerning data and cloud sovereignty. Its goal is to create a data sharing framework that includes common standards for data sharing, best practices, tools, and governance structures. It also serves as an EU-supported federation of cloud infrastructure and data services, with all 27 EU member states pledging their commitment to it.

Conversely, IDSA is a coalition comprising over 130 member companies that share a vision of a world where all companies autonomously establish usage rules and fully realise the potential of their data in secure, trusted, and equitable partnerships. The aim of this organisation is to establish a global standard for international Data Spaces (IDS) and interfaces, promoting the technologies and business models that will shape the data economy of the future across various sectors.

In essence, the evaluation of data space initiatives followed a structured approach that considered factors such as relevant project references, interoperability, the use of advanced technologies, the presence of a marketplace and innovative business models, societal impact through user engagement or co-creation, and the effectiveness of use case families.

In the end, the initiatives under review were specifically GAIA-X and IDSA. Therefore, the proposal for the GREEN.DAT.AI project emphasises a commitment to alignment among them, which are part of the DSBA. Thus, these two, along with a few others (FIWARE and BDVA/DAIRO) data space initiatives should progressively converge on a unified framework and foundational software elements at the technological level.

- **GAIA-X:** The importance of aligning with GAIA-X is significant as it outlines the project's entire architectural framework, which is particularly relevant for its implementation. The technical convergence document issued by the DSBA indicates that GAIA-X plays a crucial role in areas such as identity, compliance, registry, and trust.
 - GREEN.DAT.AI partners concentrate their efforts on engaging with GAIA-X, especially in areas related to identity, compliance, registry, and trust, by reviewing reference implementations, consulting with GAIA-X experts on these topics, and participating in GAIA-X meetings to showcase the outcomes of the implementations achieved.
 - Furthermore, there are other areas where GREEN.DAT.AI believes GAIA-X could provide a solid foundation, although other sources are also being explored. This includes, for example, the Federated Catalogue, Portal, and Data Exchange services. As in the previous case, GREEN.DAT.AI members will work with GAIA-X on these areas, seeking clarification and, if necessary, implementing the reference modules.
- **IDSA:** IDSA is also a key reference in the GREEN.DAT.AI framework as defined by the architecture and reference implementation reuse. Evaluations revealed that IDSA offers a marketplace available through the IDS App Store and is active in the connector level, providing a suite of IDSA certified modules ready for deployment, which also includes a testbed for these connectors to interact with other architectural components such as the Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS) or the Broker.

2.2 Alignment with IDSA and GAIA-X initiatives

GREEN.DAT.AI is concentrating on incorporating a certified connector from IDSA (and possibly GAIA-X) [12] to handle data exchanges and federation. Additionally, the App Store will be integrated into the project's marketplace activities. Consequently, these elements are included in the plan for discussions with IDSA in the upcoming phase to enhance alignment with IDSA and GAIA-X projects.

Regarding GAIA-X, this involves examining reference implementations, consulting with IDSA experts on relevant topics, and attending IDSA meetings to showcase the results of the implemented solutions. Other technical implementations and references to be reviewed include the Vocabulary, Broker, and Clearing House, which GREEN.DAT.AI has identified as potential modules for reuse. In this instance, these modules will be thoroughly evaluated, including their GAIA-X equivalents, to decide the most suitable strategy. This approach will also broaden the scope of engagement with IDSA to include these modules.

2.3 IDSA-compliant data sharing

Compliance is explained as ensuring that a software solution (for the current case) developed and deployed are in accordance with recognised standards, specifications, and guidelines but also applies to the process followed-up to ensure that the solution is compliant[11].

In the context of trust requirements to ensure a clear data exchange between the data provider and the data consumer, IDSA developed a rigorous and transparent certification process. Therefore, the IDS connector, as main component of a data space, requires validate its behaviour and certify it against security standards as the basis of trust that enables the exchange of data[9].

As detailed at IDSA web page “IDS defines certification scheme to define the rules, and standards of the certification process” which follows best international practices allowing organisations that will participate in a DS to pass the operational Environment Certification to ensure secure processes and management components (see **Figure 5** which shows the connectors and management components used in GREEN.DAT.AI project).

Figure 5. Mandatory components DS

Furthermore, the IDS architecture includes many components with detailed IDS specifications to protect the data to be shared by providing clear information. Also, components must pass the Component Certification process if they will be used in an IDS compliant environment.

GREEN.DAT.AI project is developing the main components of its DS based on objectives that includes different data sharing needs with the aim of validating energy efficiency of the solutions. The assessment to ensure compliance requires firstly the deployment of the DS environment and its main components to start an internal testing process focused on identify issues.

As shown in **Figure 5**, the components provided are:

1. EDC connector, responsible for accessing the DS, searching for data, contracting data exchange conditions between data providers and consumers and control the data flow between components.
2. DAPS server for Identity Management component acting as an attribute server for OAuth2 access tokens issues and enable the access to services and data of other connectors.

3. Digital clearing House for the compliance module component is a logger for the transactions, to keep the history and monitor them. It ensures traceability of data agreements.
4. The Vocabulary hub and Metadata broker as part of the Catalogue component

Likewise, as not all DS components are planned to be developed – only the mandatory ones will be developed for sure – additional tests and validations will be carried out once the use of the connector is fully operational.

Once the internal and external tests and validations have been completed, the next step will be to complete the certifications.

The development of the EDC connector has been guided by IDS’ trust and transparency standards to facilitate the certification process after the internal validations of functionalities. The deployment of connectors based on data exchange requirements of the pilots and their use case has also started enabling the internal testing and final validation.

Table 1. Status of DS mandatory components

Component	Required	Maturity	Description
IDM DAPS	Mandatory	Ready	Already deployed in the production environment.
Digital Clearing House	Mandatory	For the validation and compliance with this component, the connectors will interact with other external DS to the project. The results are expected to be available during M28 of the project.	The IDS clearing house is a logger for the transactions between connector, to keep an history and monitor them. Consequently, it will be develop based on the data exchanges performed by UCs.
Metadata Broker	Mandatory	Work in process	Expected by end of June 2024
Vocabulary Hub	Mandatory	Work in progress	Expected by end of June 2024
EDC Connector	Mandatory	Ready	Already deployed in the production environment.

2.4 Metadata Broker

The metadata broker is a critical component of the BDA infrastructure, facilitating efficient exchange and management of metadata between various data consumers and providers. This section outlines the implementation of the metadata broker within the Horizon 2020 project, leveraging advanced technologies to ensure seamless integration and robust performance.

The solution employed by GREEN.DAT.AI involves the EDC Broker Server Extension to the Sovity Data Space Connector based on Eclipse solution (EDC connector), deployed on the consortium's Kubernetes cluster. This setup is designed to optimise metadata handling through a scalable and resilient architecture.

The deployment is comprised of multiple containers within the Kubernetes cluster:

- Database Container: For metadata storage.
- Broker-UI Container: Provides the user interface.
- Broker Container: Manages backend processing and API interactions.

To ensure proper operation, the broker requires specific reverse proxy configurations to merge ports and map endpoints, ensuring secure access via TLS/HTTPS. The configuration is as follows:

Port Merging:

- UI: Port 8080
- Backend: Port 11002
- Backend: Port 11003

Mapping Configuration:

- `https://[FQDN]/backend/api/dsp -> broker-backend:11003/backend/api/dsp`
- `https://[FQDN]/backend/api/management -> broker-backend:11002/backend/api/management`
- All other requests -> broker-ui:8080

Additionally, the broker requires a ClientID for integration with a DAPS server. Once these configurations are in place, connectors can be dynamically added to the broker, enabling flexible and efficient metadata management. The broker can be accessed at <https://broker-ui-bcapper-dev.apps.ac3-cluster-1.rh-horizon.eu/>.

Summarising, to ensure that GREEN.DAT.AI data space is IDSA-compliant requires more efforts and time than the development and operation of the DS, its connectors, and mandatory components following rules and standards used by IDSA, it also requires a testing and validation process composed of the following steps:

1. Development of mandatory DS components based on the IDSA's rules and standards.
2. Test DS components before deployment on the GREEN.DAT.AI DS environment.
3. Deployment and customization of the connector per pilot site and use case.
4. Test and, finally, validate data sharing between data providers and consumers.
5. Finish testing and validation by operating the connector on an external-to-the-project data space (2nd phase).
6. Complete the certification scheme selected and complete it.

GREEN.DAT.AI project is currently performing step 3 and 4, expects to perform step 5 in the beginning of 2025 and ensure compliance (step 6) before ending the project.

2.5 Alignment with Use Cases

The GREEN.DAT.AI consortium set up a Kubernetes cluster to host services, including a reverse proxy based on Traefik [14] and an identity/authentication management service relying on Keycloak [15]. Moreover, a subdomain has been created to access the services: greendatai.ari-energy.eu.

To shape the data space, a Sovity [12] connector instance, based on Eclipse solution (EDC connector), has been deployed in the GREEN.DAT.AI cluster. Its APIs are accessible at <https://connector.greendatai.ari-energy.eu>, and its web UI is available at <https://connector-webui.greendatai.ari-energy.eu>. Credentials to work with this environment can be provided on request.

In addition, an identity management solution for the connector (**DAPS server**) has been deployed. It is a dedicated Keycloak instance, accessible at <https://keycloak-daps.greendatai.ari-energy.eu>. Full documentation about both connector and DAPS server deployment is already available in the GREEN.DAT.AI GitHub: [<https://github.com/greendatai-eu/dataspace-connector>].

Hence, the schema in **Figure 4** indicates the approach followed to address the alignment with the UCs in GREEN.DAT.AI, going from the data sources in the lower layers to the Data Space Horizontal Modules in the upper ones, while deploying a set of modules in between laying the foundation of the connector. At the moment of submission of the present report, the components that give shape to GREEN.DAT.AI solution found themselves at diverse maturity levels as shown in **Table 1. Status of DS mandatory components** with some of them already deployed in the production environment and some others in different development stages.

3. Data ingestion, harmonization, storage, and processing services

The aim of this section is to list the tools and services deployed at UCs sites instances – acting as service consumers or as data providers –, on their local data bases – including external data sources –, and/or on their orchestration services environments to ensure that the local data is processed, harmonised, transformed, and stored in the intermediary storage service (orchestration). This will ensure that the data available for sharing in the Data Space environment can be accessed by the EDC connector and sent to another connector for ingestion.

Using the initial vision of the Blueprint for a specific data platform (see **Figure 2** in chapter 2), blueprint that has been updated to reflect the changes in WP2 tasks, **Table 2** and **Table 3** details the final list of tools and services deployed at the pilot sites to manage the available data.

The data flow is initiated in local databases for the data to be transformed and stored in orchestration services. Once stored, the connector (provider) is used to publish metadata in the DS that another connector (consumer) can consume once an agreement is closed. This new connector receives the data and delivers it to the orchestration services for processing and/or integration into local databases.

Based on the initial vision of the tools and services to be deployed (see **Table 2. Tools and Services used by Local DBs and Orchestration services** and **Table 3**) list all the components that will be used by the different UCs of the project.

Table 2. Tools and Services used by Local DBs and Orchestration services

Processing Phase	Tools & Services available	Local Data Bases						Orchestration Services					
		UC1	UC2	UC3	UC4	UC5	UC6	UC1	UC2	UC3	UC4	UC5	UC6
Ingestion	Kafka			X	X	X	X			X	X	X	X
	nifi												
	minifi												
	Rest API	X	X					X	X				
	Custom connectors												
Harmonization	FIWARE												
	Smart data models												
	Custom Data models	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Storage & processing	StreamHandler	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Workflow Management Engine	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Delta lake												
	Minio												
Reporting & visualization	Visualisation Workbench	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Analytics	Distributed Analytic Services	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Workflow Management Engine	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Energy Benchmarking tWool	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Processing Phase	Tools & Services available	Local Data Bases						Orchestration Services					
		UC1	UC2	UC3	UC4	UC5	UC6	UC1	UC2	UC3	UC4	UC5	UC6
	Tools and services developed in WP3	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Data sharing	IDS Connector												
	Data Space components												
Security	KrakenD - The API Gateway and Keycloak												
	IoT Trust-based IDS					X						X	
	Data & Execution Protection												
Platform & Infrastructure	Kubernetes												

Table 3. Tools and Services used to share data using IDS connectors

Processing Phase	Tools & Services	GREEN.DAT.AI Data space						External Data Space					
		UC1	UC2	UC3	UC4	UC5	UC6	UC1	UC2	UC3	UC4	UC5	UC6
Ingestion	Kafka												
	nifi												
	minifi												
	Rest API	X	X	X	X	X	X						
	Custom connectors												
Harmonization	FIWARE												
	Smart data models												
	Custom Data models												
Storage & processing	StreamHandler												
	Workflow Management Engine												
	Delta lake												
	Minio												
Reporting & visualization	Visualisation Workbench												
Analytics	T2.3												
	Energy Benchmarking tool												
	Tools and services developed in WP3	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X			
Data sharing	IDS Connector	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	Data Space components	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Security	KrakenD - The API Gateway and Keycloak												
	IoT Trust-based IDS												
	Data & Execution Protection												
Platform & Infrastructure	Kubernetes	X	X	X	X				X	X			

3.1 Data harmonisation pipeline

The data harmonisation pipeline comprehends not only the specific tasks to homogenise the data models and the metadata but also some other important tasks that might be relevant for extracting valuable information out of the data stored. Those tasks are mainly related with data cleaning and preprocessing. Moreover, in some cases they can also include some metrics to rate the quality of the data.

As depicted in **Figure 2** the blueprint includes the harmonisation layer standing just between the data ingestion layer and the storage and processing layer. The rationale of this is to always store coherent and harmonised data that can be directly used by the upper layers without wasting time or resources in interpreting or transforming it. This approach also simplifies the visualisation of the data as it is possible to reuse existing components to provide those visualisations of different data. Finally, having harmonised data can be also helpful at data sharing level. Although the existing data space solutions, IDS and GAIA-X, both present some tools devoted to enable data sharing of uneven data, those tools (e.g., the vocabulary hub) require some level of human interaction and they are not fully automated. Thus, federating harmonised data might minimise the need for human interaction and optimise the whole workflow.

To harmonise the data there is a strong need of selecting an information model that can be compatible with all the datasets shared among the projects. One proposal would be to use NGSI-LD[17] (https://fiware-datamodels.readthedocs.io/en/stable/ngsi-ld_howto/index.html) by FIWARE which was already standardised by ETSI. This semantic information model can represent both properties and their context information. Moreover, thanks to their semantic capabilities it can establish relationships between them. Another benefit from this solution is that the data models can be serialised into JSON-LD files which make them easy to consume, send or transform.

The resulting JSON-LD files can then be stored in the data storage layers, using the already proposed components or they can be directly federated and shared through the EDC connector. In both scenarios no further data transformation shall be needed inside the project. However, it is possible that in other federations one might need to parse those data. For this reason, there is the possibility to deploy the vocabulary hub.

This component, the vocabulary hub, enables semantic interoperability among data models in different federations. As stated before, this process is not fully automatic, but it can be simplified through a wizard that can lead the person responsible for the data adaption to identify the matching fields in the different data models and create the semantic links between them.

As a result of this pipeline, the data stored or shared has better interoperability capabilities and is ready to be used by other services or consumers to get valuable information out of it.

4.2 Technical description of the Visualization Workbench component

The Visualisation Workbench is based on AVT AEGIS' tool. AVT frontend is based on Angular.io framework in conjunction with a set of visualisation libraries that are interchangeably used to cover specific needs and particularities of the analysed data. These include interactive timeline representations for time-dependent data, graph-based visualisations, chord diagrams, geospatial representations, etc.

In terms of data storage capabilities, AVT can operate with its own storage facility (mainly Elasticsearch search engine) and/or also use multiple other sources of data, be it data streams (e.g., Kafka) or batch data (e.g., via RESTful APIs, external ES, MongoDB, etc.). This flexibility is possible due to several tailor-made converters, which can request the data from the respective data sources and transform it to a suitable format for AVT's visualization widgets. These transformations together with internal configuration options and business logic activities take place in AVT's middleware application built on Node.js.

Figure 7. AVT Technology Stack

In terms of deployment, AVT can either be fully installed as an application with moderate hardware and software requirements or can be run as a containerised application with lots of configuration options allowing its smooth integration in existing environments.

Regarding the technical pre-requisites and requirements, APIs/other methods (e.g., direct access to data) are required to get the indicator values and the generated security-related events. Streaming data are also supported (e.g., via Kafka). An Angular-based web application offers the frontend of the Advanced Visualization Toolkit. A Node.js application serves as the middleware that handles data inputs and the business logic of the toolkit. AVT can be installed as standalone application, but a dockerised version of the toolkit is also available. End-users only need a browser to access AVT.

Hardware Requirements:

- CPUs: >=2
- RAM: >=4 GB (depending on the data volume and utilised visualisations)

- Disk space: >=20 GB (depending on the data volume and utilised visualisations)

Input of the component must be provided as an API or via some other method, e.g., direct access to the relevant data. Main inputs are (TBD, domain-specific):

- Indicators (and relevant values) coming from the monitoring modules.
- The tool can be also used by users to trigger actions. These actions will mostly include selection of data sources and time periods. The data retrieval will take place using one of the aforementioned methods that will be available in the project.

Figure 8 depicts the Internal architecture of AVT and how it is utilised in the GREEN.DAT.AI project.

Figure 8. AVT's Internal Architecture in GREENDATAI

Ultimately, after complete integration, the Visualisation Workbench will retrieve both predicted and historical data from the Streamhandler using REST APIs and/or Kafka message broker. At this point in the project, the visualised data are being retrieved through REST APIs from various databases related to the use cases. The Streamhandler will interface with AVT's Middleware, facilitating seamless data flow. The AVT User Interface will communicate with the Streamhandler through this Middleware, ensuring efficient data exchange. End-users will then be able to access the comprehensive dashboards via their web browsers, providing an intuitive and interactive visualisation experience.

4.3 Alignment with UCs

The Visualisation Workbench component is meticulously developed based on the workflows reported in D3.1 [18], incorporating the respective services tailored for each UC. This foundational alignment ensures that the Visualisation Workbench not only adheres to the predefined methodologies and processes but also effectively integrates with the specific service requirements and data models of each UC. By leveraging these

detailed workflows, it provides a robust framework for visualising complex data streams, thus enhancing the analytical capabilities and decision-making processes within the GREEN.DAT.AI project.

Moreover, the Visualisation Workbench boasts several key capabilities designed to enhance user experience and data interaction. These capabilities include widget reordering, allowing users to customise their dashboards for optimal data visualisation and accessibility. Advanced filtering options enable precise data analysis, ensuring users can focus on relevant information. Additionally, robust user management and access management features provide secure and efficient control over user permissions and data access, ensuring that sensitive information is protected while maintaining usability for both expert and non-expert end-users.

Visualisation Workbench Sequence Diagram

Figure 9. Visualisation Workbench Sequence Diagram

Figure 9 outlines a draft sequence diagram, illustrating the current progress of the Visualisation Workbench's integration and functionality. A user interacts with the visualisation workbench through a GREEN.DAT.AI user interface. This involves opening the workbench in a web browser. Once a user opens the workbench, the web browser page loads. After the workbench loads, the user can select the desired functionality, depending on the use case that he/she has selected. Depending on the functionality, the visualisation workbench requests data. This data request can be done via HTTPS or FFI (Foreign Function Interface) with HTTPS RPC (Remote Procedure Call). Once the data is retrieved, it is returned to the workbench through the same channels. Finally, the visualisation workbench presents the data and results to the user.

The sequence diagram will be further refined and will be included in the upcoming D2.2 deliverable, with due date on M24.

4.3.1 UC#1 – Energy Marketplaces: Data sharing across the renewable energy sector

Regarding UC1, the objective is to facilitate knowledge sharing among stakeholders in the renewable energy sector. This UC promotes the exchange of expertise, enhances model accuracy through the integration of diverse data sources, and fosters innovation within the industry. A key focus of UC1 is to address the critical need for accurate forecasting of energy production. This capability is especially important for wind-farm owners, enabling them to effectively plan their energy sales strategies. The following WP3 services are utilised to address the needs of UC1:

- Data marketplaces using blockchain [ST3.1.2]
- Data monetisation mechanisms for data sharing [ST3.1.2]
- Privacy-preserving FL [ST3.2.2]
- Geographical Transfer Learning [T3.3]

Furthermore, the following figures are mock-ups illustrating the visualisation needs of UC1. They serve as a preliminary design, highlighting the key data points and interactive elements required to support knowledge sharing and accurate forecasting within the renewable energy sector. **Figure 10** shows the user interface (UI) that facilitates the management of cryptocurrency wallets for each participant. It serves energy traders by offering analytics on their trades, allowing for manual adjustments to trading patterns, and facilitating the transmission of trading data to the market system, as depicted in the next figure.

Figure 10. Cryptocurrency Wallet Management visualisations

Moreover, the UI depicts the output of a market engine responsible for executing models for market prediction, and a database that stores historical data, recent predictions, and client data, as shown in the following figure.

Figure 11. Market System visualisations

4.3.2 UC#2 – Smart electric vehicle charging

Regarding UC2, the objective is to implement FL-enabled smart charging for Electric Vehicles (EVs) while leveraging edge computing to deploy an intelligent charging management system. This system addresses the challenges of simultaneous EV charging under varied technical constraints. A key technical aspect is the use of FL to train AI models while ensuring data privacy. This involves orchestrating a decentralised learning process where AI models are collaboratively trained across multiple local nodes (EV chargers), eliminating the need for raw data exchange. The overarching technical objective is to achieve efficient and secure model training, allowing the EV charging infrastructure to dynamically adapt to real-time grid conditions, particularly maximizing the utilisation of Renewable Energy Sources (RES).

Another technical objective is to establish crowdsensing-enabled data-driven services for EV charging management. This involves integrating data collected from EV users' smartphones, securely transmitting it

to a central server. The challenge lies in harnessing this crowd-sensed data, including GPS coordinates, acceleration, and altitude, to enhance optimisation processes, such as estimating the State of Charge of a user's EV. Additionally, the presence of a dedicated interface on users' mobile devices allows for the creation of additional features to engage users and potentially generate revenue.

Figure 12. Electric Vehicles Charging Pool visualisations

The following WP3 services are utilized to address the needs of UC2:

- Data enrichment [ST3.1.1]
- Mobility trajectory data generation (IMN-cloning Car Trajectory Synthesis) [ST3.1.3]
- Energy (demand/consumption) forecasting of charging stations/EVs [ST3.2.1]
- Trajectory-based Battery Consumption Estimation [ST3.2.1]
- Charging station occupancy forecast [ST3.2.1]
- EV transactions data forecasts [ST3.2.1]
- Distributed optimization at the edge [ST3.2.2]
- Privacy-preserving FL [ST3.2.2]
- Algorithm Selection & Hyperparameter Tuning/AutoML [ST3.2.2]
- (weighted) FL [T3.3]

Figure 12 presents a mock-up illustrating the visualisation needs of UC2, showcasing the output of WP3 services utilised in this UC. The UC2 dashboard will feature an interactive map displaying the positions of charging stations, alongside real-time graphs illustrating the energy status of each station. Additionally, the dashboard will present forecasted voltages and power consumption for all connected devices, providing a comprehensive overview of the charging infrastructure's performance and future energy demands.

4.3.3 UC#3 – Smart farming optimisation through Digital Twins

UC3 aims to improve the Farm Manager platform using AI and digital twin solutions to optimise farming practices. Its key objective is to enhance farmer counselling services by: a) generating fertilisation maps in (near) real-time tailored to soil and crop needs, b) providing monitoring services for early detection of plant pests and diseases through (near) real-time object assessment using fused satellite images and UAV inspections, and c) offering prognostics on soil health and optimal harvesting times.

Figure 13. Farm maps visualisations

The following WP3 services are utilised to address the needs of UC3:

- Data generation based on images [ST3.1.3]
- Explainable feature learning [ST3.2.3]
- (weighted) FL [T3.3]
- Orchestration framework for derivation geospatial data products [T3.4]
- Behaviour modelling pipelines [T3.4]
- Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox [T3.5]

The figure above presents a mock-up illustrating the visualisation needs of UC3, showcasing the output of WP3 services utilised in this UC. The dashboard to be developed will feature adaptive maps that display predictions of crop development, early detection of pests and diseases, and the generation of fertilisation and spraying maps. This comprehensive visualisation tool will support farmers in optimising their practices and improving overall farm management efficiency.

4.3.4 UC#4 – Smart water management

UC4 aims to provide farmers with a predictive system for irrigation water quality, meeting the growing demands of agriculture. It seeks to benefit farm managers by improving their awareness of current and future water quality, enabling adjustments for optimal crop conditions and increased productivity. The system will include a) remote real-time data intake from diverse water sources, b) integration of this data with open-source micro-location data like weather and temperature, c) identification of suitable water types and treatment methods for agriculture, d) AI-driven optimization of water intake, and e) real-time visual maps displaying water sources and quality elements.

Figure 14. Water Data visualisations

The following WP3 services are utilised to address the needs of UC4:

- Data enrichment [ST3.1.1]
- Explainable feature learning [ST3.2.3]
- Orchestration framework for derivation geospatial data products [T3.4]
- Event detection on fused datasets [T3.4]
- Behaviour modelling pipelines [T3.4]
- Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox [T3.5]

The figure above presents a mock-up illustrating the visualisation needs of UC4, showcasing the output of WP3 services utilised in this UC. This serves as a preliminary design, highlighting the key data points and interactive elements required to support UC4's objectives. The dashboard to be developed will display water quality data, water quality predictions, and irrigation optimisation data. This comprehensive tool will provide farmers and farm managers with critical insights, enabling them to make informed decisions to enhance irrigation practices and overall farm productivity.

4.3.5 UC#5 – Energy demand response in e-bikes & infrastructure planning

UC5 centers on improving energy demand response in e-bikes and infrastructure planning. Its main goal is to optimise energy demand, stabilise networks, and improve user satisfaction through a dedicated application. The objective is to strategically position fully charged e-bikes at stations with anticipated demand, facilitating distributed charging. This method aims to minimise peak energy usage, maintain network stability, and decrease the necessity for extensive bike redistribution.

Figure 15. Bikes and Stations visualisations

The following WP3 services are utilized to address the needs of UC5:

- Data enrichment [ST3.1.1]
- Mobility trajectory data generation (IMN-cloning Car Trajectory Synthesis) [ST3.1.3]
- Energy (demand/consumption) forecasting of charging stations/EVs [ST3.2.1]
- Algorithm Selection & Hyperparameter Tuning/AutoML [ST3.2.2]
- Geographical Transfer Learning [T3.3]
- (weighted) FL [T3.3]
- Event detection on fused datasets [T3.4]
- Data Ingestion Service and Analysis Toolbox [T3.5]
- Accelerated Event Processing Engine [T3.5]

Figure 15 presents a mock-up illustrating the visualisation needs of UC5, showcasing the output of WP3 services utilised in this UC. Serving as a preliminary design, it highlights the key data points and interactive elements necessary to support UC5's objectives. The dashboard to be developed will feature a map and graphs depicting the live status of the system, including the current positions of bikes and charging stations. Additionally, it will support work orders for field operators, indicating which bikes to move and where to place them, ensuring efficient management of e-bike distribution and charging.

4.3.6 UC#6 – Fraud detection and efficient explainable AI with privacy preservation

UC6 is dedicated to enhancing the effectiveness of Fraud Detection systems, recognising the increasing importance of digital security given the rise in fraud technologies. The primary focus is on developing tools to reduce operational costs at CXB by enhancing the efficiency of Fraud Detection Systems. Additionally, efforts are made to enhance customer satisfaction by employing eXplainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) to mitigate discrimination. This UC comprises four main sub-UCs: 1) XAI for secure ecommerce fraud detection, 2) XAI for detecting fraudulent enrolments in online multi-factor authentication (MFA), 3) XAI models for handling customer claims regarding potential frauds, and 4) eXplainable clustering and anomaly detection in customer behaviour.

The following WP3 services are utilized to address the needs of UC6:

- Interpretable Clustering [ST3.2.3]
- Knowledge discovery tools on learned features [ST3.2.3]
- Explainable feature learning [ST3.2.3]

The following figure presents a mock-up illustrating the visualisation needs of UC6, showcasing the output of WP3 services utilised in this UC. Serving as an initial design, it highlights the key data points and interactive elements necessary to support UC6's objectives. The dashboard to be developed will assist in fraud prevention by enabling employees to review potential fraud cases, particularly when claims are made by clients. This tool will provide a comprehensive overview, facilitating efficient detection and management of fraudulent activities, thereby enhancing the security and effectiveness of the fraud detection system.

Figure 16. Model Performance visualisations

5. Distributed analytics services and workflow management

This section describes the outcomes of T2.3, which is the StreamHandler Platform and the Workflow Management Engine (WME). Both components are part of Data orchestration element of the GREEN.DAT.AI RA as depicted in **Figure 2**. The **Streamhandler Platform** facilitates communication, data transferring, data exchange, and results sharing among all the included services in each Service Participant of the GREEN.DAT.AI RA, in a real-time, scalable, and fault-tolerant manner. The platform is based on Apache Kafka and is paired with monitoring tools for better overview and supervision of the transmitted data across or within GREEN.DAT.AI components. The **Workflow Management Engine (WME)** is responsible for supporting the definition, the scheduling, and the execution of the complex AI workflows, coming from the AI models of WP3 activities. The operations of this module are implemented on Apache Airflow tool. The communication of each Service Participant with any other DS element (DS Common Services, Pilot Participants, other Tech Provider Participants) is realised by implementing and using a dedicated DS Connector in a secure manner.

5.1 Streamhandler Platform

The StreamHandler Platform facilitates the data orchestration of GREEN.DAT.AI components and services due to its ability to enable seamless communication and data exchange in a real-time, scalable, and fault-tolerant manner. In a complex ecosystem like GREEN.DAT.AI, where multiple services and components need to interact and share data continuously, a robust platform that ensures reliable data transfer is essential. Apache Kafka, the backbone of the StreamHandler Platform, provides the necessary infrastructure to handle high-throughput and low-latency data streams, enabling the system to process vast amounts of data efficiently. This ensures that analytic processes and ML models receive timely and accurate data, which is critical for maintaining the overall performance and effectiveness of the system.

Moreover, the StreamHandler Platform enhances the interoperability and integration capabilities of GREEN.DAT.AI. By supporting multiple communication protocols and data storage services, and employing embedded connectors, the platform ensures that various components within the architecture can communicate effortlessly, regardless of their underlying technologies. This interoperability is essential for creating a cohesive and unified data ecosystem, allowing for smooth data flow and coordination across different services. Additionally, the integration with monitoring tools like Prometheus and Grafana provides comprehensive oversight and supervision of data transmissions, ensuring any issues are quickly identified and addressed. This holistic approach to data orchestration not only improves the reliability and efficiency of GREEN.DAT.AI operations but also enhances the scalability and adaptability of the platform to meet future demands and challenges.

In a nutshell, the StreamHandler platform supports real-time data streaming pipelines facilitating effective communication between GREEN.DAT.AI components, aligned with the GREEN.DAT.AI RA. The platform is an interoperable tool employing embedded connectors and offering efficient integration with multiple communication protocols and data storage services. In the subsequent sections, an in-depth examination of the StreamHandler's platform architecture, description, topics, and deployment is presented.

5.1.1 Architecture and Description

The StreamHandler platform is a high-performance distributed streaming platform based on Apache Kafka [22] for handling real-time data in a secure manner [22], achieving both low latency and high throughput. It can efficiently ingest and handle massive amounts of data into processing pipelines, for both real-time and batch processing, being an effective communication middleware service. It also offers high scalability, high fault-tolerance since it is resilient to node failures and supports automatic recovery and significantly

considers the security aspects by employing encryption, authentication, and authorisation mechanisms. The high-level architecture of StreamHandler is presented in **Figure 17** below:

Figure 17. StreamHandler high-level architecture diagram

The StreamHandler platform is built and executed on top of Apache Kafka, exploiting the advantages and features offered by this technology stack. Thus, it supports communication under TCP protocol and is interoperable and easily integrated to multiple IoT technologies and communication protocols such as MQTT. The platform can connect to multiple and different types of databases either relational, such as PostgreSQL, or NoSQL - schemeless databases, such as MongoDB. Additionally, StreamHandler module ensures secure and encrypted communication between brokers and clients by utilising SSL/TLS. This is achieved by providing each Broker and Client of the cluster with their own encryption key and their certificate for identification. For authentication purposes, brokers and clients are configured with a trust store to distinguish allowed certificates. Finally, it can be utilized if needed as a centralized logging and monitoring system with UI tools for all the connected GREEN.DAT.AI components to supervise their performance and the exchanged data.

The used Apache Kafka stack supports the integration with multiple external systems and communication mechanisms through the provided Connector API. MQTT protocol is included in those features and the corresponding connector is employed to achieve seamless integration. It can be used to transfer bidirectionally IoT data from the MQTT broker to Kafka, a solution widely applied to the IoT industry. The integration of the MQTT and Kafka brokers is achieved configuring connectors labelled as source for the forwarding of the messages from MQTT to Kafka and tagged as sink for transmitting data from Kafka to the MQTT. The implementation was tested using dummy cases to ensure seamless operation.

The development of an embedded storage system was considered to maintain records of the transmitted data through the StreamHandler platform. This undertaking involved the seamless integration of Kafka connectors with MongoDB, resulting in the design of dedicated and pre-configured connectors for each Kafka topic. The main purpose of this operation is to enable real-time storage of the information transferred through the streaming platform into a MongoDB. This functionality offers easy access and retrieval of all the data from the database. Additionally, it serves as a resource for historical data analysis and acts as a backup mechanism to ensure data integrity and resilience. In **Figure 18** below the running instance of StreamHandler is depicted.

Figure 18. Active StreamHandler instance

A sample configuration of a connector that is subscribed to a Kafka topic and stores the incoming data into a designated collection within MongoDB is shown below:

```
{
  "name": "mongodb-sink-greendatai-data",
  "config": {
    "connector.class": "com.mongodb.kafka.connect.MongoSinkConnector",
    "tasks.max": 1,
    "topics": "greendatai.<pilot>.<component>.<description>",
    "mongodb.connection.uri": "mongodb://{IP address or Hostname}:{port}",
    "mongodb.collection": "TestPilotCollection",
    "key.converter": "org.apache.kafka.connect.json.JsonConverter",
    "key.converter.schemas.enable": false,
    "value.converter": "org.apache.kafka.connect.json.JsonConverter",
    "value.converter.schemas.enable": false
  }
}
```

The platform underwent several modifications to meet GREEN.DAT.AI requirements regarding the data orchestration layer and the models from the ML services. The StreamHandler is also used for sharing results from the AI predictive tools to the Visualisation Workbench component. Among other functions, the platform is responsible for achieving seamless and secure integration in a distributed manner. This tool is applicable to specific cases and interactions (mainly within the IoT concept), leveraging the major benefits of streaming functionalities identified by some component owners and the respective needs of some pilots to fulfil their goals.

Currently, the StreamHandler platform contributes to the pilots UC3 and UC4 and UC5 for the data exchange from the sources to the modules and the sharing of the results from the AI components as well as facilitate the communication with the visualisation tool. There are plans to support more interactions both components and pilots related in the future if necessary.

5.1.2 Topics

The Apache Kafka ecosystem operates with client producers and consumers subscribed to corresponding Kafka topics where information is transmitted. The naming pattern for creating new topics to ensure a common approach and understanding is defined as follows: Prefix.pilot.component.description. Table 4 presents a topic example where "Prefix" is the keyword "greendatai," "pilot" is the keyword related to the project pilot the data pertains to (e.g., "itc," "serveo"), "component" is the keyword related to the system that publishes the message (e.g., "kontool," "automl"), and "description" is the keyword related to the type of information exchanged (e.g., "weather," "energyconsumption," "forecast," "predictions"). All the messages defined within GREEN.DAT.AI scope are in JSON format, to avoid inconsistencies and compatibility issues in the structure and the format of the exchanged data.

Table 4. Example of topic details.

Topic	Description	Sample Messages
greendatai.<pilot>.<component>.<description>	The topic where the <pilot> pilot data messages related to the <description> from <component> are published.	{ "attr1": "temp1", "attr2": 10, "attr3": 95.2, "timestamp": "2023-02-10T15:04:47.149Z", "attr4": "temp" }

The topics defined in StreamHandler platform for the needs of GREEN.DAT.AI pilots and components are presented per partner/organization in **ANNEX II – StreamHandler Topics**.

5.1.3 Deployment

The StreamHandler platform was deployed in the GREEN.DAT.AI common infrastructure to support data exchange across defined interactions (within components). Specifically, the StreamHandler platform was deployed on a cloud server within INTRA's infrastructure using Docker containers [23]. This approach facilitates both the development and deployment process of the platform and enforces its scalability and interoperability. Additionally, the platform was integrated with MongoDB to store transmitted data for testing and backup purposes. The deployment process was comprised of several scripts, including a docker-compose.yaml file that includes the necessary services, networks, and volumes for platform execution, and an env file that specified the environment variables for configuring the running infrastructure.

A sample from the docker-docker.yaml file is shown below:

```
version: '3.8'

services:
  zookeeper:
    build: ./zookeeper
    restart: unless-stopped
    hostname: ${ZOOKEEPER_HOSTNAME}
    container_name: ${ZOOKEEPER_CONTAINER_NAME}
    image: ${DOCKER_REG}${DOCKER_REPO}sh-zookeeper:${DOCKER_TAG}
    ports:
      - "${ZOOKEEPER_PORT}:${ZOOKEEPER_PORT}"
    environment:
      KAFKA_HEAP_OPTS: "-Xmx128m -Xms128m"
      ZOOKEEPER_SERVER_ID: 1
```

```

ZOOKEEPER_CLIENT_PORT: "${ZOOKEEPER_PORT}"
ZOOKEEPER_SERVERS:
"zookeeper:${ZOOKEEPER_SERVER_1_FOLLOWER_PORT}:${ZOOKEEPER_SERVER_1_ELECTION_PORT}"
env_file:
- .env
networks:
- kafka-network
volumes:
- zookeeper-data:/var/lib/zookeeper/data
- zookeeper-logs:/var/lib/zookeeper/log

kafka:
build: ./kafka
restart: unless-stopped
hostname: ${KAFKA_HOSTNAME}
container_name: ${KAFKA_CONTAINER_NAME}
image: ${DOCKER_REG}${DOCKER_REPO}sh-kafka:${DOCKER_TAG}
ports:
- "${KAFKA_EXTERNAL_PORT}:${KAFKA_EXTERNAL_PORT}"
environment:
KAFKA_HEAP_OPTS: "-Xmx1024m -Xms1024m"
KAFKA_ZOOKEEPER_CONNECT: "${ZOOKEEPER_HOSTNAME}:${ZOOKEEPER_PORT}"
KAFKA_LISTENERS:
INTERNAL://${KAFKA_INTERNAL_HOSTNAME_OR_IP}:${KAFKA_INTERNAL_PORT},EXTERNAL://${KAFKA_I
INTERNAL_HOSTNAME_OR_IP}:${KAFKA_EXTERNAL_PORT}
KAFKA_ADVERTISED_LISTENERS:
INTERNAL://${KAFKA_INTERNAL_HOSTNAME_OR_IP}:${KAFKA_INTERNAL_PORT},EXTERNAL://${KAFKA_
EXTERNAL_HOSTNAME_OR_IP}:${KAFKA_EXTERNAL_PORT}
KAFKA_LISTENER_SECURITY_PROTOCOL_MAP: INTERNAL:PLAINTEXT,EXTERNAL:PLAINTEXT
KAFKA_INTER_BROKER_LISTENER_NAME: INTERNAL
KAFKA_BROKER_ID: 1
KAFKA_NUM_PARTITIONS: 3
KAFKA_OFFSETS_TOPIC_REPLICATION_FACTOR: 1
KAFKA_OFFSETS_TOPIC_NUM_PARTITIONS: 3
KAFKA_DELETE_TOPIC_ENABLE: 'true'
KAFKA_AUTO_CREATE_TOPICS_ENABLE: 'true'
KAFKA_OFFSETS_COMMIT_TIMEOUT_MS: 60000
KAFKA_GROUP_MAX_SESSION_TIMEOUT_MS: 60000
env_file:
- .env
networks:
- kafka-network
volumes:
- kafka-data:/var/lib/kafka/data
depends_on:
- zookeeper

kafka-connect:
build: ./kafka-connect
hostname: ${KAFKA_CONNECT_HOSTNAME}

```

```

container_name: ${KAFKA_CONNECT_CONTAINER_NAME}
image: ${DOCKER_REG}${DOCKER_REPO}sh-kafka-connect:${DOCKER_TAG}
ports:
  - "${KAFKA_CONNECT_PORT}:${KAFKA_CONNECT_PORT}"
environment:
  CONNECT_BOOTSTRAP_SERVERS: "kafka:9094"
  CONNECT_REST_ADVERTISED_HOST_NAME: "kafka-connect"
  CONNECT_REST_PORT: ${KAFKA_CONNECT_REST_PORT}
  CONNECT_GROUP_ID: ${KAFKA_CONNECT_GROUP_ID}
  CONNECT_CONFIG_STORAGE_TOPIC: docker-connect-configs
  CONNECT_OFFSET_STORAGE_TOPIC: docker-connect-offsets
  CONNECT_STATUS_STORAGE_TOPIC: docker-connect-status
  CONNECT_KEY_CONVERTER: org.apache.kafka.connect.json.JsonConverter
  CONNECT_VALUE_CONVERTER: org.apache.kafka.connect.json.JsonConverter
  CONNECT_INTERNAL_KEY_CONVERTER: "org.apache.kafka.connect.json.JsonConverter"
  CONNECT_INTERNAL_VALUE_CONVERTER: "org.apache.kafka.connect.json.JsonConverter"
  CONNECT_CONFIG_STORAGE_REPLICATION_FACTOR: "1"
  CONNECT_OFFSET_STORAGE_REPLICATION_FACTOR: "1"
  CONNECT_STATUS_STORAGE_REPLICATION_FACTOR: "1"
  CONNECT_CONFLUENT_TOPIC_REPLICATION_FACTOR: 1
  CONNECT_PLUGIN_PATH: '/usr/share/java'
env_file:
  - .env
networks:
  - kafka-network
depends_on:
  - zookeeper
  - kafka

mongo-db:
  image: mongo:latest
  hostname: ${MONGO_DB_HOSTNAME}
  container_name: ${MONGO_DB_CONTAINER_NAME}
  restart: unless-stopped
  environment:
    MONGO_INITDB_ROOT_USERNAME: ${MONGO_DB_USERNAME}
    MONGO_INITDB_ROOT_PASSWORD: ${MONGO_DB_PASSWORD}
  expose:
    - "${MONGO_DB_PORT}"
  ports:
    - "${MONGO_DB_PORT}:${MONGO_DB_PORT}"
  command: --bind_ip_all --smallfiles
  networks:
    - kafka-network
  volumes:
    - mongodb-data:/data

networks:
  kafka-network:
    name: ${KAFKA_NETWORK}

```

```
driver: bridge

volumes:
  zookeeper-data:
    name: ${ZOOKEEPER_DATA}
  zookeeper-logs:
    name: ${ZOOKEEPER_LOGS}
  kafka-data:
    name: ${KAFKA_DATA}
```

A sample from the .env file is shown below:

```
## Config Network
KAFKA_NETWORK=greendatai-kafka-network

## Config Volumes
ZOOKEEPER_DATA=greendatai-zookeeper-data
ZOOKEEPER_LOGS=greendatai-zookeeper-logs
KAFKA_DATA=greendatai-kafka-data

## Config Zookeeper
ZOOKEEPER_HOSTNAME=greendatai-zookeeper
ZOOKEEPER_CONTAINER_NAME=greendatai-zookeeper
ZOOKEEPER_PORT={port}
ZOOKEEPER_SERVER_1_FOLLOWER_PORT={port}
ZOOKEEPER_SERVER_1_ELECTION_PORT={port}

## Config Kafka
KAFKA_HOSTNAME=greendatai-kafka
KAFKA_CONTAINER_NAME=greendatai-kafka
KAFKA_EXTERNAL_PORT={port}
KAFKA_EXTERNAL_HOSTNAME_OR_IP={IP address}
KAFKA_INTERNAL_PORT={port}
KAFKA_INTERNAL_HOSTNAME_OR_IP=kafka

## Kafka Connector
KAFKA_CONNECT_HOSTNAME=greendatai-kafka-connector
KAFKA_CONNECT_CONTAINER_NAME=greendatai-kafka-connector
KAFKA_CONNECT_PORT={port}
KAFKA_CONNECT_REST_PORT={port}
KAFKA_CONNECT_REST_HOSTNAME=greendatai-connector
KAFKA_CONNECT_GROUP_ID=compose-greendatai-connector

## Mongo
MONGO_DB_HOSTNAME= greendatai-mongo-db
MONGO_DB_CONTAINER_NAME=greendatai-mongo-db
MONGO_DB_USERNAME={username}
MONGO_DB_PASSWORD={password}
MONGO_DB_PORT= {port}
```

The scripts facilitating the deployment process of the platform along with the corresponding instructions for the deployment can also be found on the repository created in the GREEN.DAT.AI GitHub: <https://github.com/greendatai-eu/greendatai-streamhandler-platform>. Access to the repository hosting the code of the StreamHandler platform is allowed only to authorised users, and external members can acquire access by request.

5.2 Workflow Management Engine

In today's data-driven world, the ability to define and manage complex workflows is crucial for organisations seeking to leverage advanced analytics and ML. A WME is essential for streamlining these processes, providing a structured and systematic approach to designing, scheduling, and executing ML workflows. By automating these tasks, the WME reduces the potential for human error, increases efficiency, and ensures consistency in the execution of analytic processes. This capability is particularly important in environments where multiple workflows need to be managed concurrently, and where the complexity and interdependencies of tasks can quickly become overwhelming without a robust management system.

Moreover, the automated orchestration of analytics services through a WME significantly enhances an organisation's ability to respond to real-time data and changing conditions. The WME facilitates seamless integration and coordination of various tools and services, enabling a more agile and flexible approach to analytics. This not only accelerates the deployment of ML models but also ensures that analytic insights are delivered in a timely manner, thereby enhancing decision-making processes. The modular architecture of a WME, which allows for independent development, deployment, and scaling of services, further contributes to its importance by providing the scalability and adaptability needed to meet the evolving demands of modern analytics and ML applications.

The WME is a tool implemented in the scope of T2.3 to support the orchestration of the ML workflows designed within GREEN.DAT.AI UCs. In the following sections the architecture, the functionalities, and the deployment of the WME platform are presented in detail.

5.2.1 Architecture

The WME is designed and implemented based on cutting edge technologies applied widely in the software industry. It is a platform built on open-source tools and consist of multiple modules. It includes Apache Airflow, which is licensed to the Apache Software Foundation (ASF) under one or more contributor license agreements under the Apache License, Version 2.0, which is based in two main pillars. The WME Airflow Core and the WME Airflow worker node which are critical parts of the WME and operate collaboratively with the other implemented services as embedded elements of the platform. The WME Airflow Core and the WME Airflow worker node are used to build and execute the designed workflows as DAGs (Direct Acyclic Graphs). A DAG is a collection of tasks, organized with dependencies and relationships that define how they should be executed (order, scheduling, retries). The key capabilities and features of Airflow include scalability to manage multiple distributed workers, dynamic pipelines, extensibility to connect with numerous technologies, flexibility with built-in workflow parametrization. Those features led to the usage of the tool supporting and enhancing the design methodology.

The role of the (WME as mentioned above is to support the definition, scheduling, execution, and orchestration of ML workflows. The tool is consisted of multiple modules that are cooperating to fulfil the seamless and smooth execution of the ML workflows. The backend service is used to define, manage, and store the entities used for the structuring of the workflows. The backend communicates with the User Interface to exchange the necessary settings provided by the user to configure the workflows. The backend

also communicates with the Airflow core and Airflow workers to transfer the configuration details of the workflow to the execution phase through Airflow. Airflow core is used as the tool to execute the workflows in the distributed environments and provide monitoring, overview and statistics of the workflows' executions, where the Airflow workers are the clients running in the worker nodes and receive the execution details and commands from the Airflow Core. The selected design and approach promote a modular architecture as depicted in **Figure 19**, where services can be developed, deployed, and scaled independently.

Figure 19: Workflow Management Engine architecture diagram

5.2.2 Description

The WME is designed to enhance the management of the ML workflows within GREEN.DAT.AI project, focusing on the core processes of definition, scheduling, execution, and orchestration. The tool is consisted of multiple modules as presented in the previous section that are cooperating to run the ML workflows. Central to the WME's architecture is the Backend Service, which serves as the critical hub for defining, managing, and storing essential entities that structure these workflows. This service is integral to the system, facilitating the exchange of the necessary settings between the user interface and the backend, thereby

allowing users to configure their workflows precisely. Additionally, it plays a fundamental role in workflow coordination, interfacing seamlessly with Airflow components to orchestrate the execution process efficiently.

Incorporating Airflow into the WME significantly reinforces its capability to manage workflow executions in distributed environments. The Airflow Core manages the workflow processes, providing robust monitoring capabilities that deliver critical statistics and overviews of workflow executions. Complementing this are the Airflow Workers, client applications running on worker nodes that execute tasks as directed by the Airflow Core. On the user interface, the WME offers an interactive platform that enables users to configure and modify workflow details through an intuitive interface and to monitor and manage executions, viewing real-time statistics and controlling ongoing workflows. This ensures that users not only have the tools to set up their workflows efficiently but also the capability to manage them actively, enhancing overall workflow performance.

In this section, the key features of the WME will be explored, with a special emphasis on the user interface (UI) where user interactions occur. The UI of the WME offers a diverse range of operations and functionalities, and is composed of several pages, each designed for specific functions. The three primary pages are "Resources," "Lab," and "Airflow." In the following sections, we will delve into the features and purposes of each page in detail.

5.2.2.1 Resources page

Initially, the "Resources" page offers a comprehensive overview of the user's available and configured assets. This page is organized into four main tabs, specifically labelled as "MY WORKFLOWS," "MY WORKERS," "MY DATA SOURCES," and "MY OPERATORS," each designed to provide easy access and management of different aspects of the user's resources.

First, the "MY WORKFLOWS" tab provides users with a clear snapshot of all created workflows. Here, users can efficiently filter their workflows based on names or creation dates. Each workflow is uniquely identified by an automatically generated ID at the time of creation. Additional details such as the workflow's name and a description are also available, which are initially defined in the "Overview" section of the "Lab" page, as illustrated in **Figure 20** below. Furthermore, the creation date of each workflow is displayed for easy reference.

Figure 20. WME "Resources" page and Workflows tab

On this page, users have several actionable options. By clicking the folder icon (1), users can view a specific workflow, which redirects them to the "Lab" page for a more detailed examination. For workflow management, users can delete any workflow by clicking the bin icon (2), as shown in **Figure 20** below. To

initiate a new workflow, users can click the "CREATE NEW WORKFLOW" button (3), which also redirects them to the "Lab" page where they can configure the new workflow's settings.

The "MY WORKERS" tab displays all the workers currently registered within the system, which are capable of executing workflows. Users have the flexibility to run a workflow on a single worker or distribute it across multiple workers. This distribution allows for the scattering of ML tasks and operators across several workers, enhancing the efficiency of the workflow execution.

Several actions are available to users within this tab for managing their workers as depicted in **Figure 21**. By clicking the folder icon (1), users can view detailed information about a specific worker. If a user needs to remove a worker from the system, they can do so by clicking the bin icon (2). To add a new worker to the system, users can click the "ADD WORKER" button (3). This action opens the "Add a Worker" window, which contains a form where the user can enter all necessary information to configure a new worker.

Figure 21. WME Workers tab

The form for adding a new worker, as depicted in **Figure 22**, is structured to gather comprehensive information through multiple fields. The "General Information" section requires inputs such as the "Name" and "Description" of the worker, which help in identifying and understanding the purpose of the worker within the system.

In the "Details" section, users are asked to provide specific configuration settings for the worker. This includes entering the IP address, an SSH user, and the SSH public key. These details are essential for enabling secure access to the worker via the WME, facilitating the execution of workflows.

Figure 22. WME "Add a Worker" window

Additionally, the form includes a "Tags" section, which allows users to assign descriptive tags to the worker. These tags can include identifiers such as 'cloud', 'testing', 'CPU', 'GPU', 'Keras', or 'TensorFlow'. These tags are useful for categorizing workers based on their capabilities, specifications, or the tools they support, making it easier to manage and deploy the right resources for specific workflows.

The "MY DATA SOURCES" tab provides users with an overview of all available data sources within the system. This tab allows users to effectively filter and locate data sources by name or creation date, offering streamlined access and management. Each data source listed is uniquely identified by an ID, which is automatically generated at the time of its creation. Additionally, essential details such as the name, a brief description, and the creation date of each data source are displayed, as illustrated in **Figure 23**. This setup ensures that users can quickly and efficiently manage their data resources, enhancing the overall workflow management process.

Figure 23. WME Data Sources tab

Within the "MY DATA SOURCES" tab, users are equipped with specific actions to efficiently manage their data sources. By clicking the folder icon (1), users can view detailed information about a particular data source, facilitating a deeper understanding of its content and structure. To remove a data source that is no longer needed, users can click the bin icon (2), as depicted in **Figure 23**.

Figure 24. WME "Add a Data Source" window

For adding new data sources to the system, users can utilize the "ADD DATA SOURCE" button (3). Clicking this button opens the "Add a Data Source" window, which presents a form requiring various details to be filled in. This form, shown in **Figure 24**, collects essential information about the new data source, ensuring

that it is properly configured and integrated into the system. This streamlined process allows users to quickly expand and customize their data environment, enhancing the overall functionality and efficiency of their workflows.

Currently, the system supports a variety of data source types, which are categorized under "Data Interface Type" in the user interface. These types are accessible via a drop-down list in the corresponding section, allowing users to select the appropriate interface for their needs. The available options include REST API, Kafka brokers, and Elastic Stack. There is ongoing planning to expand this list to include additional data source types as required by user demand and system capabilities.

Future expansions are expected to incorporate relational databases such as PostgreSQL, as well as No-SQL databases like MongoDB, broadening the scope of data integration within the platform. Each interface type comes with dedicated configurations, ensuring that users can customise their data sources according to specific requirements and characteristics of the data interface. This structured approach facilitates efficient data management and integration, enhancing the overall utility and flexibility of the system.

For data sources utilizing REST APIs, specific configurations are required to ensure seamless integration and secure communication with the system. These configurations include the URL address of the API, the method of interaction—such as GET, POST, etc.—and a token for authorisation, which is necessary to access the endpoint securely. These detailed settings are crucial for establishing a reliable connection to the API, allowing for efficient data retrieval or submission. Each of these configuration options is clearly outlined and can be easily set up by the user, as shown in **Figure 25**. This setup ensures that users can customise their API connections to meet specific security and data interaction requirements.

The screenshot shows a configuration interface titled "Details". On the left, there is a dropdown menu labeled "Data Interface Type" with "API REST" selected. Below this is a green notification box with a question mark icon and the text "REST API configuration template created for project GreenDataAI.". To the right of the dropdown are three input fields: "url", "method", and "Auth Bearer Token".

Figure 25. WME Data Sources details for REST API

For integrating Kafka as a data source, specific prerequisite settings are necessary to ensure proper connectivity and data flow. These settings include the broker URL, which is the address of the Kafka broker, the broker port, and the specific topic to which the operator needs to connect. These configurations are essential for establishing a successful connection to the Kafka system, enabling effective data streaming and management. Users must input these details accurately to facilitate seamless integration with Kafka's distributed streaming platform. Each of these configuration parameters is clearly depicted and can be easily configured through the user interface, as illustrated in **Figure 26**. This setup ensures optimal data transmission and accessibility within the Kafka environment.

Details

Data Interface Type

Kafka Interface
▼

broker url

port

topic

? Kafka interface template created for project GreenDataAI.

Figure 26. WME Data Sources details for Kafka interfaces

For Elastic cases the needed information is the IP, the port and the index to get the data as shown in **Figure 27**.

Details

Data Interface Type

Elastic Interface
▼

IP

port

index

? Elastic interface template created for project GreenDataAI.

Figure 27. WME Data Sources details for Elastic interfaces

The "MY OPERATORS" tab showcases the available operators within the system. This tab is closely connected to the "Lab" page, particularly under the "Flow Creator" tab. Operators are defined and created in the "Flow Creator" section by clicking the "ADD NODE" button as presented in upcoming paragraphs, where a list of available operators is presented and can be updated. In the "MY OPERATORS" tab, users are limited to viewing the operators only. To create a new operator as highlighted in **Figure 28**, users must navigate back to the "Lab" page and access the "Flow Creator" view to select "ADD NODE". This process facilitates the addition of new operator nodes into the workflow.

The information displayed for each operator in this view includes the name, description, and ID of the operator, as well as details regarding the number of data inputs and outputs associated with each operator. This detailed display helps users quickly identify and understand the capabilities and role of each operator within their workflows, ensuring efficient workflow management and customization.

Operator Name	Description	Operator Type ID (in use)	Data Input	Data Output	Actions
T3.4 - Orchestration framework for derivation geospatial data products	UC4 model for Orchestration framework for derivation geospatial data products	664f05e71e8bc3576023e0bd	Sources Count: 1	Target Count: 1	
T3.4 Behaviour modeling pipelines	UC4 model for Behaviour modeling pipelines	664f05e71e8bc3576023e0bd	Sources Count: 1	Target Count: 1	
ST3.1.1 - Data enrichment	UC4 model for Data enrichment	664f05e71e8bc3576023e0bd	Sources Count: 1	Target Count: 1	
T2.2 Visualization Workbench	Visualization Workbench	664f05e71e8bc3576023e0bd	Sources Count: 2	Target Count: 0	

i Operators can only be created during the workflow building process!

Figure 28. WME Operators tab

The interface offers users several actions. As depicted in **Figure 28**, by clicking on the folder icon (1), users can view details about the operator; by clicking on the bin icon (2), they can delete the operator. Upon selecting the folder icon (1), a window displays, as shown in **Figure 29**, presenting the operator's details. These details encompass the operator's Name, Description, Type, Deployment, and Data Flow. Users have the option to update this information as needed.

Figure 29. WME "Edit an Operator" window

5.2.2.2 Lab page

Having examined the “Resources” page and its supporting features, the analysis proceeds to the “Lab” page which is the primary workspace of WME UI for creating and configuring workflows. It features three main tabs, the "WORKFLOW SPECIFICATIONS", the "FLOW CREATOR" and the "OVERVIEW". Each tab is dedicated to different aspects of workflow management and setup.

In the "WORKFLOW SPECIFICATIONS" tab, users enter configuration details for the workflow as shown in **Figure 30**. The “Basic DAG Configurations” section includes several options. The option “Is Paused Upon Creation” determines whether the DAG is paused upon its initial creation. If the DAG already exists, this setting is disregarded. If left unspecified, the configuration defaults to the global settings. The setting “Keep Alive” defines whether the infrastructure should remain active continuously. The option “Catchup” allows for either a scheduler catchup, where it runs missed executions, or only the most recent execution for the DAG. The default setting is "True". The choice “Requires Scheduler” specifies whether setting up a scheduler is necessary for the workflow's execution. The scheduling options are extensive, allowing for precise timing

configurations (year, month, week, day, hour, minutes). There are also the options “Start Date” and for “End Date”, which define correspondingly the time for the initial execution of the flow and the final execution. Each of these settings plays a crucial role in designing the workflow's behaviour to specific requirements.

Figure 30. WME "Lab" page and "Workflow Specifications" tab

The “FLOW CREATOR” tab as shown in **Figure 31**, serves as the interactive workspace and canvas where users can design and construct their workflows. This tab provides the tools and interface necessary for visually assembling workflow components and defining their interconnections.

Figure 31. WME Flow Creator tab and view of workflows

To add a new node to the workflow, users can click the "Add node" button, which opens a form as illustrated below. In this form, users can input the operator's details and configurations across four main categories, the "General Information", the "Details", the "Deployment" and the "Data Flow."

The "CLEAR" button allows users to erase all entered details across these categories. Conversely, the "SAVE" button enables users to save the newly created node, which will then be visible in the "FLOW CREATOR" view, as depicted in **Figure 32**. Furthermore, as shown in **Figure 33**, once a node is created, users have the flexibility to modify it by clicking the "EDIT NODE" button or remove it using the "DELETE NODE" button. This functionality ensures that users can easily manage and update nodes within their workflow.

Figure 32. WME "Add an Operator" window

Figure 33. WME workspace and node view

The form for adding an operator is segmented into four primary sections. It begins with the "General Information" section, where users input the operator's name and provide a descriptive overview.

Figure 34. WME "Add an operator" details for Docker executors

Next, the "Details" section allows users to specify the operator type and its associated settings. As illustrated in **Figure 34**, one example of an operator type is an executor that utilizes Docker containers. This configuration requires three specific fields, the Container Name, which is the name assigned to the Docker container upon execution, the Docker Registry, which is the repository where the Docker image is stored and the Container Port which defines the network port that the container will expose. Additionally, a "USE DEFAULTS" button is available in this section, which populates the fields with predefined example values, simplifying the configuration process.

The operator type "Cleaner," another available executor type depicted in **Figure 35**, is designed to manage and clear running tasks within the execution environment. This functionality is crucial for maintaining operational efficiency and ensuring that resources are appropriately allocated by removing or terminating tasks that are no longer needed or are consuming excessive resources.

Figure 35. WME "Add an operator" details for cleaner executors

In the "Deployment" section, as illustrated in **Figure 36**, users can select a worker from the list of available resources to carry out the task. Upon selection, the details of the chosen worker will be displayed, providing critical information such as the worker's capabilities, current load, and any special configurations. This step ensures that the task is assigned to a worker that is best suited for its requirements, optimising the execution process.

Figure 36. WME "Add an operator" deployment details for the worker to execute the operator

In the final section of the form, "Data Flow," users need to specify the data sources associated with this operator. As depicted in **Figure 37**, this involves defining both the "Data Input" and "Data Output." Users must detail the source from which the operator will retrieve data (Data Input) and where the processed data will be directed (Data Output). This setup ensures that data flows seamlessly through the workflow, from ingestion to output, facilitating effective data handling and processing.

Figure 37. WME "Add an operator" Data flow options

In the "Data Flow" section, the available options for "Data Input" and "Data Output" are derived from the "Data Sources" defined on the "Resources" page. These options are presented in a dropdown list, allowing users to conveniently select the appropriate sources and destinations for their data. As shown in **Figure 38** below, this dropdown feature facilitates quick and accurate configuration of data pathways, ensuring that the operator integrates smoothly with the existing data environment.

Figure 38. WME "Add an operator" Data flow details for the sources the operator is connected

The "OVERVIEW" screen, as displayed in **Figure 39**, provides a comprehensive snapshot of the workflow, incorporating several key elements. The "Details" part includes the name of the workflow and a brief description, giving users a quick overview of the workflow's purpose and scope. Moreover, there are control buttons for the newly created workflows. There are options to save, clear, or delete the workflow. For existing workflows, an additional option to update the workflow is available, allowing for modifications and refinements. The "Stats" section displays statistics for the nodes within the workflow, providing insights and assistance in managing and optimizing the workflow. Finally, the "Download DAG File" button offers to the users the option to download the DAG file of the created workflow. This feature is particularly useful for backup, sharing, or further customisation outside the platform. These components ensure that users have all the necessary tools and information for effective workflow management directly from the overview screen.

Figure 39. WME "Lab" page "Overview" tab

5.2.2.3 Airflow page

Following the comprehensive description of the "Lab" page, the document transitions to discussing the "Airflow" page. This page facilitates access to the Apache Airflow environment, which is seamlessly integrated using an iframe. This integration enables users to oversee, monitor, and manage executed workflows and provides detailed insights into the DAGs, cluster activities, and the overall configuration of Airflow.

The "DAGs" list provides a comprehensive display of all created DAGs, serving as a tool for users managing and monitoring their workflows. This list not only presents each DAG but also examines detailed aspects of their executions. Users can view whether DAGs are queued, successfully completed, or have failed, providing immediate insight into the operational status. Additionally, the list includes scheduling information, showing the time of the last execution and when the next one is planned, which is critical for effective time management and planning.

Figure 40. WME "Airflow" page and overview

The status of individual tasks within each DAG is also available, offering users a granular view of the workflow's components. Furthermore, actionable controls are provided, allowing users to either trigger a

new execution or delete a DAG directly from the list, as illustrated in **Figure 40**. This integration of detailed data and user control makes the DAGs list an essential feature for efficient workflow management.

As shown in **Figure 41**, the “DAG screen” offers a detailed view of a specific DAG. This screen is particularly valuable for users who need to understand the details of individual DAG operations. It presents a comprehensive list of commands that have been executed, alongside detailed reports of each run. This setup enables users to analyse the performance and outcomes of their workflows thoroughly, ensuring they can make informed decisions and adjustments to optimise future executions. The DAG screen is an essential tool for deep diving into the operational aspects of each DAG, providing clarity and control over complex workflow management tasks.

Figure 41. WME "Airflow" page and DAG details

The WME interface by incorporating the Airflow, as depicted in **Figure 42**, provides a detailed overview of cluster activities, crucial for monitoring and managing the execution of the DAGs. This interface displays comprehensive information about each DAG, including its execution type—whether manual or scheduled. Additionally, it shows the current status of these DAGs, categorising them as successful, failed, or running, which helps users quickly assess the operational health of their workflows.

Figure 42. WME "Airflow" page and cluster activities overview

Further enhancing its utility, the interface also reports on the states of the involved tasks. Users can see briefly which tasks have succeeded, failed, or are queued, allowing for immediate and informed responses to any issues that may arise. This detailed presentation of both DAGs and task statuses in the WME interface ensures that users have all the necessary information to effectively oversee complex clusters and maintain optimal workflow performance.

5.2.3 Deployment

The deployment of the WME is performed on the cloud infrastructure of the project hosted by INTRA using the automated deployment pipelines from the advancements of the CI/CD tools and stack running for the project. Containerized packaging using Docker Containers [21] is used for the deployment of all the different modules of WME and are executed in a distributed way in multiple Virtual Machines (VMs). This distributed approach offers a greater efficiency, reliability, and better resource utilisation. The usage of docker containers offer flexibility and ensure that the software executed properly without issues regardless of the deployment platform and infrastructure (local machine, on-premises servers, or cloud environments), and this is an important factor since the GREEN.DAT.AI involves multiple UCs and may require multiple deployments in other premises.

Moreover, this packaging offer faster development and deployment, since the containers streamline the CI/CD pipeline by providing consistent environments for development, testing, and deployment, along with quick updates on the applications and roll back to previous versions if needed, facilitating continuous delivery and deployment. Finally, an important factor highly considered within GREEN.DAT.AI and one of a major objectives is the reduced energy consumption and the efficient resource usage. To that end, containers share the host OS kernel and, they are lighter and more efficient than virtual machines, allowing more containers to run on the same hardware, by efficiently using server resources, containers can reduce infrastructure costs and energy consumption.

The docker containers for all the WME components are created by dedicated “docker-compose.yaml” files and “.env” files including the necessary configurations for their execution. As mentioned, the WME is comprised of the User Interface, the Backend services, the Airflow Core, and the Airflow workers. In the following sections, sample “docker-compose.yaml” and “.env” files are presented for each WME module.

User Interface sample docker-compose.yaml

```
version: '3.7'

services:
  wme-ui:
    image: node:lts-alpine
    container_name: wme-ui
    ports:
      - "{ports}:{ports}"
    volumes:
      - ./ui:/app
    networks:
      - "wme-network"
    command:
      - /bin/sh
      - -C
```

```
- |
  cd /app
  install
  npm run dev
```

```
networks:
  wme-network:
```

```
volumes:
  mongodb_data
```

Backend sample docker-compose.yaml

```
version: '3.7'

services:
  app:
    build: .
    container_name: workflow-management-engine
    ports:
      - "{port}:{port}"
    environment:
      SPRING_DATA_MONGODB_USERNAME: {username}
      SPRING_DATA_MONGODB_PASSWORD: {password}
      SPRING_DATA_MONGODB_DATABASE: reports
      SPRING_DATA_MONGODB_PORT: {port}
      SPRING_DATA_MONGODB_HOST: {IP address}
    depends_on:
      - mongodb
    networks:
      - "wme-network"

  mongodb:
    image: mongo:latest
    container_name: mongodb-container
    environment:
      MONGO_INITDB_ROOT_USERNAME: {username}
      MONGO_INITDB_ROOT_PASSWORD: {password}
    ports:
      - "{port}:{port}"
    volumes:
      - mongodb_data:/data/db
    networks:
      - "wme-network"

networks:
  wme-network:

volumes:
  mongodb_data:
```

Airflow core sample docker-compose.yaml

```

version: '3'

x-airflow-common:
  &airflow-common
  build: ./airflow_docker
  environment:
    &airflow-common-env
    ##### AIRFLOW
    AIRFLOW__CORE__FERNET_KEY: ${AIRFLOW_FERNET_KEY:-}
    AIRFLOW__CORE__LOAD_EXAMPLES: 'false'
    AIRFLOW__CORE__EXECUTOR: CeleryExecutor
    AIRFLOW__CORE__ENABLE_XCOM_PICKLING: 'true'
    AIRFLOW__CORE__DAGS_ARE_PAUSED_AT_CREATION: 'true'
    AIRFLOW__API__AUTH_BACKENDS:
'airflow.api.auth.backend.basic_auth,airflow.api.auth.backend.session'
    AIRFLOW__DATABASE__SQL_ALCHEMY_CONN:
postgresql+psycopg2://airflow:airflow@postgres/airflow
    _PIP_ADDITIONAL_REQUIREMENTS: ${_PIP_ADDITIONAL_REQUIREMENTS:-}
    AIRFLOW__WEBSERVER__SECRET_KEY: ${AIRFLOW_WEB_SECRET_KEY:-}
    ##### CELERY
    AIRFLOW__CELERY__TESTY_TEST: "test"
    AIRFLOW__CELERY__FLOWER_HOST: 0.0.0.0
    AIRFLOW__CELERY__BROKER_URL: redis://:@redis:${REDIS_TLS_PORT}/0
    AIRFLOW__CELERY__RESULT_BACKEND: "db+postgresql://airflow:airflow@postgres/airflow"
    AIRFLOW__CELERY__FLOWER_BASIC_AUTH: ${CELERY_WEB_UNAME}:${CELERY_WEB_PSSWD}
    AIRFLOW__CELERY__ACCEPT_CONTENT: 'auth'
    AIRFLOW__CELERY__TASK_SERIALIZER: 'auth'
    AIRFLOW__CELERY__EVENT_SERIALIZER: 'auth'
    AIRFLOW__CELERY__SECURITY_KEY: ${WORKER_SSL_KEY_FILE:-}
  extra_hosts:
    - "remote_worker01:{IP address}"
  volumes:
    - ./security:/security
    - ./dags:/opt/airflow/dags
    - ./logs:/opt/airflow/logs
    - ./plugins:/opt/airflow/plugins
    - ./env:/opt/airflow/.env
    - /etc/docker/certs.d:/etc/docker/certs.d
    - /usr/bin/docker:/usr/bin/docker
    - /var/run/docker.sock:/var/run/docker.sock
  depends_on:
    &airflow-common-depends-on
    redis:
      condition: service_healthy
    postgres:
      condition: service_healthy

services:
  postgres:

```

```
image: postgres:13
# command: >
environment:
  POSTGRES_USER: {username}
  POSTGRES_PASSWORD: {password}
  POSTGRES_DB: {database}
ports:
  - ${POSTGRES_PORT}:${POSTGRES_PORT}
volumes:
  - postgres-db-volume:/var/lib/postgresql/data
  - ./security:/security
healthcheck:
  test: ["CMD", "pg_isready", "-U", {username}]
  interval: 5s
  retries: 5
  restart: always

redis:
image: redis:7.2
ports:
  - ${REDIS_TLS_PORT}:${REDIS_TLS_PORT}
volumes:
  - ./security:/security
healthcheck:
  test: >
    redis-cli ping
  interval: 5s
  timeout: 30s
  retries: 50
  restart: always

airflow-webserver:
<<: *airflow-common
command: webserver
ports:
  - ${AIRFLOW_WEB_PORT}:${AIRFLOW_WEB_PORT}
healthcheck:
  test: ["CMD", "curl", "--fail", "http://${HOST_IP}:${AIRFLOW_WEB_PORT}/health"]
  interval: 10s
  timeout: 10s
  retries: 5
  restart: always
depends_on:
  <<: *airflow-common-depends-on
airflow-init:
  condition: service_completed_successfully

airflow-scheduler:
<<: *airflow-common
command: scheduler
```

```
healthcheck:
  test: ["CMD-SHELL", 'airflow jobs check --job-type SchedulerJob --hostname "${HOST_IP}"]
  interval: 10s
  timeout: 10s
  retries: 5
  restart: always
  depends_on:
    <<: *airflow-common-depends-on
  airflow-init:
    condition: service_completed_successfully
```

```
airflow-triggerer:
  <<: *airflow-common
  command: triggerer
  healthcheck:
    test: ["CMD-SHELL", 'airflow jobs check --job-type TriggererJob --hostname "${HOST_IP}"]
    interval: 10s
    timeout: 10s
    retries: 5
    restart: always
  depends_on:
    <<: *airflow-common-depends-on
  airflow-init:
    condition: service_completed_successfully
```

```
airflow-init:
  <<: *airflow-common
  entrypoint: /bin/bash
  command:
    - -c
    - |
      {Checks before execution}
  environment:
    <<: *airflow-common-env
    _AIRFLOW_DB_MIGRATE: 'true'
    _AIRFLOW_WWW_USER_CREATE: 'true'
    _AIRFLOW_WWW_USER_USERNAME: ${_AIRFLOW_WEB_UNAME}
    _AIRFLOW_WWW_USER_PASSWORD: ${_AIRFLOW_WEB_PSSWD}
  user: "0:0"
  volumes:
    - ./sources
```

```
airflow-cli:
  <<: *airflow-common
  profiles:
    - debug
  environment:
    <<: *airflow-common-env
    CONNECTION_CHECK_MAX_COUNT: "0"
  command:
```

```
- bash
--c
-airflow
```

flower:

```
<<: *airflow-common
command: celery flower --basic-auth=${CELERY_WEB_UNAME}:${CELERY_WEB_PSSWD}
environment:
  <<: *airflow-common-env
ports:
  - ${CELERY_FLOWER_PORT}:${CELERY_FLOWER_PORT}
healthcheck:
  test: ["CMD", "curl", "--fail", "http://${HOST_IP}:${CELERY_FLOWER_PORT}/"]
  interval: 10s
  timeout: 10s
  retries: 5
restart: always
depends_on:
  <<: *airflow-common-depends-on
airflow-init:
  condition: service_completed_successfully
```

volumes:

```
postgres-db-volume:
```

Airflow core sample .env file

```
# AIRFLOW USERS || DC.C
AIRFLOW_UID=1000
DOCKER_GID=990
AIRFLOW_WEB_PORT={port}
AIRFLOW_WWW_UNAME_USERNAME={username}
AIRFLOW_WEB_PSSWD={password}
AIRFLOW_WEB_SSL_CERT=/security/airflow/airflow.pem
AIRFLOW_WEB_SSL_KEY=/security/airflow/airflow-key.pem
AIRFLOW_CA_CERT=/security/ca/rootCA.pem
AIRFLOW_WEB_SECRET_KEY={key}
AIRFLOW_FERNET_KEY={key}

# HOST || DC.C
HOST_IP={IP address}
# WORKER_NAME=worker01

# REDIS || DC.C
REDIS_TLS_PORT={port}
REDIS_TLS_CERT_FILE=/security/redis/redis.pem
REDIS_TLS_KEY_FILE=/security/redis/redis-key.pem
REDIS_TLS_CA_CERT_FILE=/security/ca/rootCA.pem
REDIS_TLS_CLIENT_CERT_FILE=/security/redis/redis-client.pem
REDIS_TLS_CLIENT_KEY_FILE=/security/redis/redis-client-key.pem
```

```
# POSTGRES      || DC.C
POSTGRES_PORT={port}
POSTGRES_SSL_CERT_FILE=/security/postgres/postgres.pem
POSTGRES_SSL_KEY_FILE=/security/postgres/postgres-key.pem
POSTGRES_SSL_CA_FILE=/security/ca/rootCA.pem

# Celery        || DC.C
CELERY_WEB_UNAME={username}
CELERY_WEB_PSSWD={password}
CELERY_FLOWER_PORT={port}
CELERY_FLOWER_CERT=/security/flower/flower.pem
CELERY_FLOWER_KEY=/security/flower/flower-key.pem
CELERY_FLOWER_CA_CERT=/security/ca/rootCA.pem
```

Airflow workers sample docker-compose.yaml

```
version: '3'
x-airflow-common:
  &airflow-common
  build: ./airflow_docker
  environment:
    &airflow-common-env
    AIRFLOW__CORE__EXECUTOR: CeleryExecutor
    AIRFLOW__DATABASE__SQL_ALCHEMY_CONN:
postgresql+psycopg2://airflow:airflow@postgres/airflow
    AIRFLOW__API__AUTH_BACKENDS:
'airflow.api.auth.backend.basic_auth,airflow.api.auth.backend.session'

    AIRFLOW__CORE__FERNET_KEY: ${AIRFLOW_FERNET_KEY:-}
    AIRFLOW__CORE__ENABLE_XCOM_PICKLING: 'true'
    AIRFLOW__CORE__LOAD_EXAMPLES: 'false'

    AIRFLOW__CORE__DAGS_ARE_PAUSED_AT_CREATION: 'true'
    _PIP_ADDITIONAL_REQUIREMENTS: ${_PIP_ADDITIONAL_REQUIREMENTS:-}
    AIRFLOW__WEBSERVER__SECRET_KEY: ${AIRFLOW_WEB_SECRET_KEY:-}
    AIRFLOW__CELERY__FLOWER_HOST: 0.0.0.0
    AIRFLOW__CELERY__BROKER_URL: redis://:@redis:${REDIS_TLS_PORT:-6379}/0
    AIRFLOW__CELERY__RESULT_BACKEND: "db+postgresql://airflow:airflow@postgres/airflow"
    ##### AIRFLOW
    AIRFLOW__CELERY__FLOWER_BASIC_AUTH:                                ${CELERY_WEB_UNAME:-
celery}:${CELERY_WEB_PSSWD:-celery}
    ## Worker
    AIRFLOW__CELERY__ACCEPT_CONTENT: 'auth'
    AIRFLOW__CELERY__TASK_SERIALIZER: 'auth'
    AIRFLOW__CELERY__EVENT_SERIALIZER: 'auth'
    AIRFLOW__CELERY__SECURITY_KEY: ${WORKER_SSL_KEY_FILE:-}

services:
  airflow-worker:
    <<: *airflow-common
    build: ./airflow_docker
```

```

container_name: ${WORKER_NAME:-remote_worker}
ports:
  - "{port}:{port}"
hostname: ${WORKER_NAME}
command: celery worker -H ${WORKER_NAME}@${HOST_IP} -q ${WORKER_NAME} -v
extra_hosts:
  - "redis: {IP address}"
  - "postgres: {IP address}"
# command: version
# command: airflow db init
# command: ["celery", "worker", "-l", "info"]
# command: celery flower
volumes:
  - ${TB_LOGS_PATH}:/opt/airflow/tb_logs
  - ./security:/security
  - ./dags:/opt/airflow/dags
  - ./logs:/opt/airflow/logs
  - ./data:/opt/airflow/data
  - ./models:/opt/airflow/models
  - ./plugins:/opt/airflow/plugins
  - ./env:/opt/airflow/.env
  - /etc/docker/certs.d:/etc/docker/certs.d
  - /usr/bin/docker:/usr/bin/docker
  - /var/run/docker.sock:/var/run/docker.sock
  - /usr/libexec/docker:/usr/libexec/docker
environment:
  <<: *airflow-common-env
  DUMB_INIT_SETSID: "0"
healthcheck:
  test:
    - "CMD-SHELL"
    - 'celery --app airflow.executors.celery_executor.app inspect ping -d "celery@${AIRFLOW_IP}"'
  interval: 10s
  timeout: 10s
  retries: 5
  restart: always

```

Airflow worker sample .env file

```

# HOST      || DC.C
AIRFLOW_IP={IP address}
AIRFLOW_WEB_SECRET_KEY= {key}
AIRFLOW_FERNET_KEY=' {key}
HOST_IP= {IP address}

# WORKER    || DC.W
WORKER_NAME=remote_worker01
WORKER_SSL_KEY_FILE=/security/${WORKER_NAME}/${WORKER_NAME}-key.pem
WORKER_SSL_CERT_FILE=/security/${WORKER_NAME}/${WORKER_NAME}.pem
WORKER_SSL_CERT_STORE=/security/ca/rootCA.pem

```

```
# REDIS      || DC.C
REDIS_TLS_PORT={port}
REDIS_TLS_CERT_FILE=/security/redis/redis.pem
REDIS_TLS_KEY_FILE=/security/redis/redis-key.pem
REDIS_TLS_CA_CERT_FILE=/security/ca/rootCA.pem
REDIS_TLS_CLIENT_CERT_FILE=/security/redis/redis-client.pem
REDIS_TLS_CLIENT_KEY_FILE=/security/redis/redis-client-key.pem

# ARTIFACTORY  || CONFIG
ARTIFACTORY_HOST=harbor.greendatai.rid-intrasoft.eu/{port}
ARTIFACTORY_REGISTRY='/mlops'
ARTIFACTORY_USER={username}
ARTIFACTORY_PSSWD={password}

# KAFKA      || CONFIG
KAFKA_TOPIC={topic}
KAFKA_BROKER= {IP address}:{Port}
KAFKA_CONSUMER_GROUP='CONS_ML_DATA'

# TENSORBOARD  || CONFIG
TB_LOGS_PATH=/home/greendatai/mlops/tensorboard01/tb_logs

# MODULES LIB
MODULES_LIB_PATH=/modules
```

The scripts facilitating the deployment process of the WME along with the corresponding instructions for the deployment can also be found on the dedicated repositories created in the GREEN.DAT.AI GitHub to host the code for each module. More specifically for the WME core backend and user interface the repository <https://github.com/greendatai-eu/workflow-management-engine>, for the setup of the remote workers the <https://github.com/greendatai-eu/workflow-management-engine-worker> and for the embedded Airflow tool <https://github.com/greendatai-eu/workflow-management-engine-airflow>. The access to the repository hosting the code of the WME tool is allowed only to authorized users, and external members can acquire access by request

6. Wrappers for Securing Computations and Sensitive Data at the Edge/Fog/Cloud

In Task 2.4 “Wrappers for Securing Computations and Sensitive Data at the Edge/Fog/Cloud”, tools that are responsible for ensuring the security, trustworthiness, and confidentiality of devices and data that exist within the GREEN.DAT.AI ecosystem have been developed, enhanced, and adapted to GREEN.DAT.AI requirements considering the infrastructure characteristics. This section of the deliverable presents all the relevant development, deployment, and integration details of these tools. **Table 5. Tools resulting from Task 2.4 “Wrappers for Securing Computations and Sensitive Data at the Edge/Fog/Cloud”** outlines the tools that have been offered in GREEN.DAT.AI through Task 2.4. **Figure 3** shows the how the Security Wrappers reside in the most recent RA of the GREEN.DAT.AI platform. The tools that are part of the Security Wrappers are displayed using blue rectangles in the Reference Architecture.

Table 5. Tools resulting from Task 2.4 “Wrappers for Securing Computations and Sensitive Data at the Edge/Fog/Cloud”

Tool Name	Tool Owner	Objective
IoT Trust-based Network Intrusion Detection System (NIDS)	TUC	Detection of compromised machines in the network
Data and Execution Protection using Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs)	TUC	Data and execution protection using remote attestation in TEEs
Security Component	STS	Authentication management and secure transmission of data

6.1. IoT Trust-based Network Intrusion Detection System

The “IoT Trust-based NIDS” tool, as part of the Security Wrappers developed in Task 2.4, aims to monitor and detect compromised machines that exist in the network. Machines, when compromised, can exhibit anomalous behaviour in traffic conditions. Thus, each instance of the “IoT Trust-based NIDS” tool monitors a single network interface, analyses its attributes and assigns a trust value to each IP address detected in the network traffic.

As long as the traffic received from a specific IP address respects the trust value assigned, the IP address is considered trustworthy. The trust values span according to the condition to be met. Specifically, an instance of the “IoT Trust-based NIDS” tool checks if the network traffic meets one or more network traffic conditions. Examples of such conditions can be the observed throughput, or the packet frequency as transmitted from a single IP address. **Figure 43** displays a high-level overview of the “IoT Trust-based NIDS” architecture. As shown in this figure, the “IoT Trust-based NIDS” monitors the network traffic that passes through a single network interface (NIC).

The tool can be customised and configured according to the user requirements, as shown in this figure. For instance, a user can set two conditions on a single network interface: (i) the throughput threshold set to a specific value, and (ii) the packet rate not to exceed a specific frequency. Except for setting the expected conditions in terms of network traffic rates, declaring meta-characteristics that indicate suspicious IP addresses is possible. For instance, machine fingerprints can be constructed to exclude the communication with specific machines (e.g., machines that participate in botnets). More information about the process of fingerprint construction is presented in the paper entitled “Fingerprinting the Shadows: Unmasking Malicious Servers with ML-Powered TLS Analysis” [10], the implementation and publication of which was supported by

the GREEN.DAT.AI project. The configuration of the “IoT Trust-based NIDS” filters are customised based on the user requirements.

Figure 43. High-level overview of the IoT Trust-based Network Intrusion Detection System (NIDS)

During the runtime, the relevant values per IP address (e.g., number of packets sent) are updated. The “IoT Trust-based NIDS” then, calculates a “pass” or “fail” flag based on the configurations set by the user. While an IP address does not exceed any condition threshold, then the “pass” flag is set. Similarly, if an IP address exceeds certain thresholds, then the “fail” flag is marked. The resulting tuple of those values is used to update the “Trust Factor” of the “IoT Trust-based NIDS”.

A “Trust Factor” is assigned to a single IP address and its initial value is set to neutral. A snapshot of a configuration file that was used as an example is presented in **Figure 44**. The value of this “Trust Factor” keeps fluctuating according to the activity of the IP address. The real-time identification of suspiciously acting network nodes (i.e., those that exceed specific thresholds set) enables the fast detection and blocking of compromised devices.

```

"trust_thresholds_low": 25,
"trust_thresholds_max": 100,
"trust_thresholds_neutral": 50,
"trust_thresholds_penalty": 5,
"trust_thresholds_reward": 1

```

Figure 44. A snapshot of the “IoT Trust-based NIDS” thresholds as set in the configuration file

For the purposes of a demonstration of the “IoT Trust-based NIDS” operation, the tool is executed on a laboratory machine (with IP address “192.168.0.11”). The tool captures the network traffic of the network interface named “eth0”. From a different machine in the infrastructure (its IP address is “192.168.0.12” and reference to this machine is as “offending node”), we target the machine executing the “IoT Trust-based NIDS” and transmit network packets with higher rates than expected. Specifically, the LINUX utility tool nping is executed using the following command “nping 192.168.0.11 --tcp --rate 1500 --count 3500”. As expected,

- Docker image uploaded to Harbor
- Jenkins pipeline configured and added
- To access the host network interfaces, the following docker run arguments were required: --cap-add NET_ADMIN --net=host -e IFACE="eth0"
- The Jenkins pipeline was scheduled/started.

The output of the tool after its deployment on INTRA cloud is presented in the following figure.

```

2024/04/03 14:04:45 devnode-greendatai capture[1]: (info) kit (trustIds): skip 140.82.121.5, 4 packets
2024/04/03 14:04:45 devnode-greendatai capture[1]: (info) kit (trustIds): 49.13.154.91: packets=165, duration=6545613767.000000, packetrate=25.207720
2024/04/03 14:04:45 devnode-greendatai capture[1]: (info) kit (trustIds): 49.13.148.40: packets=445, duration=17120841498.000000, packetrate=25.991713
2024/04/03 14:04:45 devnode-greendatai capture[1]: (info) trust (thresholds): reward 49.13.154.91
2024/04/03 14:04:45 devnode-greendatai capture[1]: (info) trust (thresholds): 49.13.154.91 52 -> 53
2024/04/03 14:04:45 devnode-greendatai capture[1]: (info) trust (thresholds): reward 49.13.154.91
2024/04/03 14:04:45 devnode-greendatai capture[1]: (info) trust (thresholds): 49.13.154.91 53 -> 54
2024/04/03 14:04:45 devnode-greendatai capture[1]: (info) trust (thresholds): reward 49.13.148.40
2024/04/03 14:04:45 devnode-greendatai capture[1]: (info) trust (thresholds): 49.13.148.40 52 -> 53
2024/04/03 14:04:45 devnode-greendatai capture[1]: (info) trust (thresholds): reward 49.13.148.40
2024/04/03 14:04:45 devnode-greendatai capture[1]: (info) trust (thresholds): 49.13.148.40 53 -> 54
2024/04/03 14:04:45 devnode-greendatai capture[1]: (info) kit (trustIds): 62.1.224.211: packets=386, duration=8930122689.000000, packetrate=43.224490
2024/04/03 14:04:45 devnode-greendatai capture[1]: (info) trust (thresholds): reward 62.1.224.211
2024/04/03 14:04:45 devnode-greendatai capture[1]: (info) trust (thresholds): 62.1.224.211 52 -> 53
2024/04/03 14:04:45 devnode-greendatai capture[1]: (info) trust (thresholds): reward 62.1.224.211
2024/04/03 14:04:45 devnode-greendatai capture[1]: (info) trust (thresholds): 62.1.224.211 53 -> 54
2024/04/03 14:04:45 devnode-greendatai capture[1]: (info) api: log: payload:
{
  "140.82.121.5": 52,
  "49.13.148.40": 54,
  "49.13.154.91": 54,
  "62.1.224.211": 54
}

```

Figure 47. The output of the “IoT Trust-based NIDS” deployed and running on INTRA cloud.

In this figure, the “Trust Factors” set per IP address are displayed. In addition, in this specific example, it can be observed that since the IP addresses respect the thresholds concerning the expected packet rates, each IP address receives a reward.

In the following months, the IoT Trust-based NIDS will be adapted to the relevant Pilots/Use Cases and integrated with the “Visualisation Workbench” of AEGIS to display the blocked devices as alerts. The adaptation and integration details will be presented in the upcoming deliverable D2.2 (due date M24).

6.2. Data and Execution Protection using Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs)

The “Data and Execution Protection using Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs)” is a tool that combines both Remote Attestation and Trusted Execution Environment technologies, to track and attest the trustworthiness of devices. This is especially effective when applied to edge devices that can be compromised and altered with malicious intent.

Remote Attestation is a mechanism in trusted computing in which a target device must verify itself to an Attestation Server also known as attester. Essentially, it is a proof that the execution environment can be trusted before starting to execute code or before delivering any secret information.

In this tool, the attester initiates the attestation process by sending a request, and the target device must prove its identity. In this specific exchange, the identity is proven by correctly responding to the encrypted request, by using a key that has been stored in a secure environment during the device setup. In addition, the process of creating the correct response is also done in that secure environment. This specific environment is known as the Trusted Execution Environment (TEE).

A TEE is a secure area of a main processor. It ensures that code and data loaded inside it are protected in terms of confidentiality and integrity. This specific tool utilizes the technology of ARM TrustZone [19], in-line with the OP-TEE specification [20].

OP-TEE is a TEE designed as a companion to a non-secure Linux kernel running on Arm processors and specifically, Cortex-A cores that use the TrustZone technology. OP-TEE implements (i) the TEE Internal Core API v1.3.1, which is the API exposed to Trusted Applications and (ii) the TEE Client API v1.0, which is the API describing how to communicate with a TEE.

Trusted Applications (TAs) are programs that are executed in the secure OS. These applications are invoked by Client Applications (CAs) that reside in the normal OS (non-secure OS). In this tool’s case, the implemented CA is responsible for redirecting the request (packet) from the attester to the secure OS and receiving the response from the secure OS to send it to the attester. The TA is responsible for securely storing and loading the cryptographic key, as well as executing decryption/encryption securely.

The “Data and Execution Protection using TEEs” tool deploys an environment known as Trusted Execution Environment on edge nodes. Essentially each node sets up a “Listener” (TCP server), expecting TCP packets in the form of requests. These packets are crafted by a central host named “Attester” and are sent after specific time intervals. Each request is essentially a random number that is encrypted by a set key specified by the administrator for each node. A node that receives an encrypted request then proceeds to decrypt it in the Secure OS, as well as utilising the secure storage capabilities of the TEE technology to store and load the key for decryption/encryption. If it successfully decrypts the number sent by the “Attester”, it increments that number by one value, encrypts the new number and sends it back to the connected socket. Finally, the attester can determine whether the attestation attempt was successful or not. Of course, this procedure runs periodically, to ensure the fast detection of tampered and untrusted devices in the infrastructure. **Figure 48** presents how the attestation process is achieved with the tool “Data and Execution Protection using TEEs”.

Figure 48. The attestation cycle of the tool “Data and Execution Protection using TEEs”.

Specifically, the remote attestation procedure includes the following steps:

1. The attester crafts an encrypted packet (based on the target device's secret key), containing a number.
2. The Normal OS of the edge device receives the packet and if the port number is the same one as the one specified for the TEE, the Normal OS invokes the Trusted Application to process the received packet.
3. The TA loads the secret key from the secure storage and with it, it attempts to decrypt the packet, increment the value that was sent by the attester, and encrypt it back.
4. The Normal OS then receives the encrypted response.
5. The Normal OS sends the response back to the attester.
6. The attester then attempts to decrypt the packet and if the response is as expected, the trustworthiness of the device is verified.

Since both the secret key and the computations are executed in the Secure-OS, the Normal-OS monitors exclusively encrypted packets. This enhances the attestation process, as it is an added layer of security.

In GREEN.DAT.AI, TUC in collaboration with SERVEO, successfully deployed the “Data and Execution Protection using TEEs” tool to a BeagleBone Black board [21]. The BeagleBone boards are the edge devices used in the infrastructure of SERVEO. While the BeagleBone Black on its own is not supported by the OP-TEE specification, the deployment solution creates a virtualized environment via QEMU, emulating an ARM CPU. The tool is deployed utilising Docker, as well as pre-compiled binaries (cross compiled for both 32- and 64-bit systems) for the TEE's filesystem (this is mandatory for the cryptographic key to be stored securely).

The BeagleBone Black was sent to TUC premises for the deployment and some initial testing. A picture with the board is provided in **Figure 49**. The compiled file system and TA handle attestation requests by utilising a demo key “tuc4567890123456”.

Figure 49. A picture of the BeagleBone Black board that was sent from SERVEO to TUC premises for the deployment of the “Data and Execution Protection using TEEs” tool.

Figure 50 shows that the attester in the background terminal sends a request to the BeagleBone's IP address (connected by USB), the appropriate port that is set in the Client Application for the “Data and Execution Protection using TEEs” tool, as well as the correct key. In the right terminal, normal OS, it is observed that the listener is set up and ready to receive packets at the port number 59672. As soon as it receives the

request, indicated by “server accepted the client”, it invokes the TA responsible for handling the request. In the left terminal, secure OS, an entry point is created and the secure code, along with the secure key, can decrypt the request, increment it, and encrypt it to send it back. The attester, background terminal, receives the response and decrypts it correctly, and validate that the number it received was indeed what was expected.


```

Secure-OS (on BeagleBone)
D/TC?: 0 ldef_syscall_open_bin:167 res=0xffff0000
D/TC?: 0 ldef_syscall_open_bin:163 Lookup user TA ELF 8a0cb40a-a269-4f94-8d95-252a180181f2 (Secure Storage TA)
I/TC: WARNING (insecure configuration): Failed to get monotonic counter for REE FS, using 0
I/TC: WARNING (insecure configuration): Failed to commit dirh counter 2
D/TC?: 0 ldef_syscall_open_bin:167 res=0xffff0000
D/TC?: 0 ldef_syscall_open_bin:163 Lookup user TA ELF 8a0cb40a-a269-4f94-8d95-252a180181f2 (REE)
D/TC?: 0 ldef_syscall_open_bin:167 res=0
D/LB: ldef:176 ELF (8a0cb40a-a269-4f94-8d95-252a180181f2) at 0x189000
D/TA: TA_CreateEntryPoint:50 has been called
D/TA: __GP11_TA_OpenSessionEntryPoint:79 has been called
I/TA: Hello World!
D/TA: handle_secure_payload:281 has been called
I/TA: [INCR] p_out: 607547
I/TA: [INCR] p_in: 607548
I/TA: sizeof c_out: 128
D/TC?: 0 tee_ta_close_session:460 csess 0x3c7216a8 id 2
D/TC?: 0 tee_ta_close_session:479 Destroy session
I/TA: Goodbye!
D/TA: TA_DestroyEntryPoint:61 has been called
D/TC?: 0 destroy_context:318 Destroy TA ctx (0x3c721668)
[]

Normal-OS (on BeagleBone)
MUSA device list:
No soundcards found.
Freeing unused kernel image (initramfs) memory: 1024K
Run /init as init process
Saving 256 bits of creditable seed for next boot
Starting syslogd: OK
Starting klogd: OK
Running sycstl: OK
Set permissions on /dev/tee*: OK
Create/set permissions on /data/tee: OK
Starting tee-suplicant: Using device /dev/teepriv0, OK
Starting network: OK
Starting network (udhcp): OK

Welcome to Buildroot, type root or test to login
buildroot login: root
# remote_attestation
Listening on port: 59672
=== start timer ===
server accepted the client.
=== end timer ===
execution time: 33.296187

(base) argyris@parasecurity:/home/argyris/ra_tee/src/attester$ ./tcp_client -a 192.168.7.2 -p 59672 -k tuc4567890123456 -v
sent request[192.168.7.2:59672]: 607547, response: 607548 [VALID]
(base) argyris@parasecurity:/home/argyris/ra_tee/src/attester$
  
```

Figure 50. Valid attestation of the BeagleBone board

In Figure 51 the same process as the valid attestation is performed. In this experiment, the attester sends a request crafted with a different key to emulate a possible tampering of the device. As it can be observed in Figure 51 the secure OS is unable to identify the expected number while decrypting the request. The attester, then, indicates that the response is different than expected and classifies the response as invalid.


```

Secure-OS (on BeagleBone)
D/LB: ldef:142 Loading TS 8a0cb40a-a269-4f94-8d95-252a180181f2
D/TC?: 0 ldef_syscall_open_bin:163 Lookup user TA ELF 8a0cb40a-a269-4f94-8d95-252a180181f2 (early TA)
D/TC?: 0 ldef_syscall_open_bin:167 res=0xffff0000
D/TC?: 0 ldef_syscall_open_bin:163 Lookup user TA ELF 8a0cb40a-a269-4f94-8d95-252a180181f2 (Secure Storage TA)
D/TC?: 0 ldef_syscall_open_bin:167 res=0xffff0000
D/TC?: 0 ldef_syscall_open_bin:163 Lookup user TA ELF 8a0cb40a-a269-4f94-8d95-252a180181f2 (REE)
D/TC?: 0 ldef_syscall_open_bin:167 res=0
D/LB: ldef:176 ELF (8a0cb40a-a269-4f94-8d95-252a180181f2) at 0x189000
D/TA: TA_CreateEntryPoint:50 has been called
D/TA: __GP11_TA_OpenSessionEntryPoint:79 has been called
I/TA: Hello World!
D/TA: handle_secure_payload:281 has been called
I/TA: [INCR] p_out: 951626
I/TA: [INCR] p_in: 951626
I/TA: sizeof c_out: 128
D/TC?: 0 tee_ta_close_session:460 csess 0x3c7216a8 id 2
D/TC?: 0 tee_ta_close_session:479 Destroy session
I/TA: Goodbye!
D/TA: TA_DestroyEntryPoint:61 has been called
D/TC?: 0 destroy_context:318 Destroy TA ctx (0x3c721668)
[]

Normal-OS (on BeagleBone)
Saving 256 bits of creditable seed for next boot
Starting syslogd: OK
Starting klogd: OK
Running sycstl: OK
Set permissions on /dev/tee*: OK
Create/set permissions on /data/tee: OK
Starting tee-suplicant: Using device /dev/teepriv0, OK
Starting network: OK
Starting network (udhcp): OK

Welcome to Buildroot, type root or test to login
buildroot login: root
# remote_attestation
Listening on port: 59672
=== start timer ===
server accepted the client.
=== end timer ===
execution time: 33.296187
=== start timer ===
server accepted the client.
=== end timer ===
execution time: 22.165878

(base) argyris@parasecurity:/home/argyris/ra_tee/src/attester$ ./tcp_client -a 192.168.7.2 -p 59672 -k 0000000000000000 -v
sent request[192.168.7.2:59672]: 951626, response: 951626 [INVALID]
(base) argyris@parasecurity:/home/argyris/ra_tee/src/attester$
  
```

Figure 51. Invalid attestation of the BeagleBone board due to a faulty key.

In the following months, the “Data and Execution Protection using TEEs” tool will be adapted to the SERVEO UC, and it is expected to get integrated with the “Visualisation Workbench” of AEGIS to alert for any edge device in the infrastructure that is not attested, thus untrusted. The adaptation and integration details will be presented in the following deliverables.

6.3. Security Component

For authentication and authorisation within our system, a dedicated security component will be leveraged, which integrates Keycloak for robust identity and access management, alongside KrakenD, an efficient API Gateway, to ensure secure and streamlined access to our resources and services.

This security component is designed to enhance the security architecture of applications by providing comprehensive Identity and Access Management (IAM) capabilities, alongside a robust mechanism for exposing RESTful APIs securely. It integrates two essential open-source technologies: Keycloak for IAM, and KrakenD as the API Gateway, working in tandem to ensure secure authentication and authorisation processes.

Keycloak: Identity and Access Management

Keycloak is at the heart of this component, serving as the foundation for identity and access management. It is a versatile platform that streamlines authentication process for users and services, offering a wide range of features that are critical for modern security needs. Some of the notable capabilities of Keycloak include:

- **Single Sign-On (SSO):** Enables users to log in once and access multiple applications without re-authenticating, providing a seamless user experience across a suite of services.
- **Identity Brokering:** Allows integration with external identity providers, making it easier to manage access across different platforms.
- **Social Login:** Facilitates easier access for users by allowing them to log in with their existing social media accounts, enhancing user experience and adoption.
- **User Management:** Offers robust administration tools for managing users, including registration, password policies, and user federation.
- **Authentication and Authorization:** Provides comprehensive mechanisms to authenticate users and authorise access to resources, ensuring that only entitled users can access sensitive information.

KrakenD: API Gateway

- Complementing Keycloak, KrakenD acts as the gatekeeper for APIs, managing and exposing them to the external world while enforcing access controls defined by Keycloak. As an API Gateway, KrakenD offers several features designed to optimise the performance and reliability of API interactions:
- **Authorisation Enforcement:** Integrates with Keycloak to apply access policies, ensuring that only authenticated and authorised users can access the APIs.
- **Rate Limiting:** Controls the number of requests a user can make to an API within a certain timeframe, protecting against abuse and ensuring fair use of resources.
- **Circuit Breaking:** Automatically detects failures in the backend services and temporarily blocks requests to those services, helping to maintain overall system stability.
- **Caching:** Reduces the load on backend services by caching responses, improving response times for frequently accessed data.

Combined Functionality

By combining Keycloak and KrakenD, this security component offers a holistic approach to securing applications and services. Keycloak provides the essential IAM features needed to authenticate users and manage their access, while KrakenD extends these capabilities to the realm of API management, ensuring that only authorised requests are processed and that the APIs remain performant and reliable. This integration not only secures the application landscape from unauthorised access but also enhances the scalability and performance of service interactions, making it an indispensable component of any modern security infrastructure.

Internal Architecture

Figure 52. KrakenD API Gateway setup

Figure 52 visually represents the internal architecture of the security component, illustrating the seamless interaction between authentication and authorisation processes to protect the system's APIs.

The flow within the security component architecture operates as follows:

- **Authentication:** The process begins when a user's system interacts with the KrakenD API Gateway, which communicates with Keycloak to authenticate user's credentials. Upon successful authentication, Keycloak issues an access token, which is sent back to the user's system through KrakenD.
- **Authorisation:** Once the user has an access token, any subsequent requests to access the APIs must be authorised. The user's system sends a request to KrakenD with the access token, for authorisation. KrakenD validates the token by interfacing with Keycloak. Upon successful validation, KrakenD grants access to the requested API, whether it's API 1, API 2, or API 3. This ensures that only authenticated and authorised requests reach the APIs, providing a secure environment for operations.

7. Energy Efficiency Testing Framework

The testing framework allows the provisioning of measurable and comparable evaluation results for assessing the performance of AI algorithms from several perspectives: energy, model precision, data volume, and time.

The framework includes: (1) a list of performance metrics that measure the efficiency of AI algorithms, namely FL variants, and quantify business benefits enabled by access to high-quality data and extracted knowledge. As part of the framework, a testing protocol is established to guide the collection of results, following a black-box rationale, and allowing configurable deployment options for testing, capable of enabling edge or cloud resources.

The outline of the testing framework is depicted from the perspective of the user/developer of an AI algorithm that uses the testing framework to assess a given algorithm during its development and operation stages. Ahead in the document, the perspective from the testing framework itself is also taken to depict and specify functionalities.

The main rationale considers that algorithms are sets of instructions materialised in a high-level programming language application. The codebase from algorithms is enclosed in a container package that becomes the interchangeable piece to allow testing several algorithms and rendering comparable results among different algorithms and configurations. Given their intrinsic characteristics, algorithms are grouped into classes, namely Federated Learning, Reinforcement Learning, Transfer Learning, and Forecasting.

From the user's perspective, the testing framework:

0. Deploys the testing framework tool in a capable hardware setting.

Selects a computing environment with hardware resources capable to run and collect the meaningful metrics. Requirements' details the needed resources.

1. Selects and adopts a base container for the class of algorithm to be tested.

Several classes of algorithms will be available. Each class has a codebase with links to the benchmark execution: dataset and deployment configuration. The codebase is integrated with the algorithm to be tested, and an image is packed.

2. Selects a deployment configuration (workload) and performs any customisation.

Workloads specify dimensions for the execution of the benchmark, defining: the algorithm class, the target dataset to be considered, and the target deployment configuration (i.e., edge environment, cloud environment, custom environment).

3. Sets the benchmark execution or schedules it.

The benchmark execution job is started, or it is scheduled for later execution at a given time.

4. Compute a baseline for the algorithm being to be tested.

4.1. Uses a pre-computed baseline considering reference results for that class of algorithm.

The baseline is established for each algorithm class, being computed considering a reference model and dataset. The impact is measured (via the collected metrics) by comparing the results of each benchmark execution with the reference baseline.

4.2. Computes the departing baseline for the specific algorithm.

The baseline is established as the departing version for a specific algorithm, from which an evolution curve is defined by validating the impact (via the collected metrics) of the adopted changes. When the benchmark finishes the execution, results are collected to be reviewed.

5. Reviews results and withdraws conclusions.

The metrics allow a comparison with the available baseline to support drafting conclusions and pursuing the evolution of the algorithms' design.

6. Computes KPIs that directly depend on the produced metrics.

KPIs use the defined methodology to compute results based on the metrics produced from all defined profiles.

From the Testing Framework perspective, the system:

7. Includes Modules with key functionality to operate the benchmark tests.

7.1. Dataset repository module.

The repository contains datasets to be used for different algorithm classes. Several datasets may be available for each class. For each class, a reference dataset is paired (later) with a reference model to compute a baseline, as depicted in the user perspective – step 3.1. Algorithms in each class adopt a common ingestion interface to ensure the SUT can ingest data.

7.2. Algorithm repository module.

This repository holds a starting code base with an interface that concerns the testing framework. Each algorithm will extend this interface to trigger actions such as running the benchmark’s stages and collecting the results. It is mandatory for the interfaces to be adopted.

7.3. Container Manager Module

Manages the individual containers holding the algorithms to be tested and sets up the SUT environment for the actual testing.

7.4. Metrics Module

The metrics module includes profilers to collect all the relevant metrics and handle all the specific characteristics. The following profilers are expected:

- Energy profiler: Should capture the energy expenditure of the computation and export a metric either in Watt and/or Joules with reference to a process in the scope of an operating system or regarding a container (e.g., docker).
- Model performance profiler: Relies on the mandatory interface adopted by each algorithm and exports values concerning the computed accuracy, loss, and mean square error. As much results as possible are desirable to be computed. Accuracy is a mandatory result.
- Time profiler: Observes and computes the time expended in each stage of the workload.

7.5. KPI Handler Module

Collects the results from individual metrics and hosts the computed KPIs. Holds an internal and external API, respectively interfacing with the Metrics module to collect the metrics and with other systems/clients to insert already computed KPIs.

7.6. Visualisation Module

Consumes information from the Metrics module and KPI Handler to track the results. Provides UI tools to manipulate the deployment of functionalities.

7.7. KPI Reporting Module

This optional module transforms the results of metrics and renders the results in any required format for reporting purposes.

The Energy Testing Framework includes a series of assumptions and prerequisites that allow its operation, namely:

Table 6. Testing Framework Use Case Conditions.

Use case conditions
Assumptions
1 – Energy profilers report values extracted from the processing units (CPU and GPU) which are considered correct.
2 – Only qualified CPUs are part of the underlying deployment hardware.

<p>3 – AI algorithms are a self-contained set of instructions that are deployed in a software container and adopt the testing framework interface.</p> <p>4 – Frameworks for developing and experimenting AI techniques or algorithms are considered, namely: Monai, PyTorch, Tensorflow, Keras, Scikit-Learn, PySpark, H2O)</p>
<p>Prerequisites</p>
<p>An initial code base to support algorithm execution is available. All dependencies must be configured when performing the integration of the algorithm.</p>

7.1 Architecture, Scenarios and Diagrams and Requirements

7.1.1 Architecture

The full architecture of the testing framework was introduced in D1.1[1], including the full description of components and the key purpose and rationale.

Figure 54. Architecture of the AI testing framework.

Figure 54 depicts the main modules that build the testing framework, including the supporting technologies that embody each module or from which components are built upon.

7.1.2 Scenarios and Diagrams

Table 7. AI Testing Framework Boot Scenario.

Scenario conditions						
No.	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Pre-condition	Post-condition
1	Boot	The Orchestrator boots, starts all necessary components and initializes the CUT.	Orchestrator	The benchmark is booted.	The benchmark is not executing.	The Dataset Repository, Algorithm Repository, Container Under Test, KPI Handler, KPI Reporting and Visualisation module are running. The Container Under Test successfully downloads the necessary datasets from the Dataset Repository.
1.1	Boot – Container Registry Failed	The Orchestrator aborts booting.	Orchestrator			No modules are running.
1.2	Boot – KPI Handler Failed	The Orchestrator aborts booting.	Orchestrator			No modules are running.
1.3	Boot – Dataset Repository Failed	The Orchestrator aborts booting.	Orchestrator			No modules are running.
1.4	Boot – Container Failed	The Orchestrator aborts booting.	Orchestrator			No modules are running.
1.5	Boot – Dataset Not Found	The Orchestrator aborts booting.	Orchestrator			No modules are running.
2	Start Train	The Container Under Test executes the algorithm training code with the training data and measures metrics.	Container Under Test	The Orchestrator sends a start training request.	The Container Under Test and Energy Profiler are running, and the inference phase is not executing.	The algorithm running in the CUT is trained and metrics are stored.

Scenario conditions						
No.	Scenario name	Scenario description	Primary actor	Triggering event	Pre-condition	Post-condition
2.1	Start Train – Without Energy Profiling	The Container Under Test executes the algorithm training code with the training data and measures metrics.	Container Under Test	The Orchestrator sends a start training request.	The Container Under Test is running, and the inference phase is not executing.	The algorithm running in the CUT is trained and metrics are stored.
3	Start Infer	The Container Under Test executes the algorithm with the inference data and measures metrics.	Container Under Test	The Orchestrator sends a start inference request.	The Container Under Test and Energy Profiler are running, and the inference phase is not executing.	The algorithm inference is finished, and the metrics are stored.
3.1	Start Infer – Without Energy Profiling	The Container Under Test executes the algorithm with the inference data and measures metrics.	Container Under Test	The Orchestrator sends a start inference request.	The Container Under Test is running, and the inference phase is not executing.	The algorithm inference is finished, and the metrics are stored.

Boot

Figure 56. UML Sequence Diagram for the Boot Phase of the AI testing framework.

Scenario								
Scenario name:		No. 1 – Boot						
Step No.	Event	Name of the Process of Activity	Description of process/ activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Information Exchanged (IDs)	Requirement , R-IDs
1.1	Load configuration file	Load config	The Orchestrator module loads the configuration file from the file system and stores the necessary data for execution.	GET	Orchestrator	Orchestrator		F1, F2, F3
1.2	Start the Docker Registry	Boot registry	The Container Registry is initialized.	EXECUTE	Orchestrator	Container Registry		F1
1.3	Start the KPI Handler	Boot KPI Handler	The KPI Handler is initialized.	EXECUTE	Orchestrator	KPI Handler		F4, F5, F6, F7
1.4	Start the dataset repository	Boot data repository	The Dataset Repository is initialized.	EXECUTE	Orchestrator	Dataset Repository		F2
1.5	Start container to run algorithm	Boot container	The Container Under Test is initialized.	EXECUTE	Orchestrator	Container Under Test	IE3, IE4, IE5	F8
1.6	Start measuring metrics	Start measures	Start measuring dataset download time.	EXECUTE	Container Under Test	Container Under Test		F6
1.7	Download the datasets require to	Download dataset	The Container Under Test downloads the dataset necessary for tests from the Dataset Repository.	GET	Container Under Test	Dataset Repository		F2

Scenario								
Scenario name:		No. 1 – Boot						
Step No.	Event	Name of the Process of Activity	Description of process/ activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Information Exchanged (IDs)	Requirement , R-IDs
	run the algorithm							
1.8	Stop metric measurements	End measures	Stop measuring dataset download time and collect dataset size.	EXECUTE	Container Under Test	Container Under Test		F6
1.9	Start the algorithm driver	Boot Driver	Initialize Algorithm Driver.	EXECUTE	Container Under Test	Algorithm Driver		F1
1.10	Execute the user's boot code	Run algorithm boot code	Run user made code necessary to set up tests.	EXECUTE	Algorithm Driver	Algorithm Driver		F1
1.11	Push metrics to Orchestrator	Push metrics	Send metrics collected during the boot process to the KPI Handler.	EXECUTE	Orchestrator	KPI Handler	IE1	F6
1.12	Send metrics to the KPI Handler	Send metrics	The Orchestrator sends the metrics to the KPI Handler.	EXECUTE	Orchestrator	KPI Handler	IE2	F6

Figure 57. UML Sequence Diagram for the Train Phase of the AI testing framework

Scenario								
Scenario name:		No. 2 – Start Train						
Step No.	Event	Name of process/ activity	Description of process/ activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Information Exchange (IDs)	Requirement, R-IDs
2.1	Start the training process	Start train	The Orchestrator sends training start action to the Container Under Test.	EXEC UTE	Orchestrator	Container Under Test		F8
2.2	Begin time metrics collection	Start measures	The Container Under Test starts time measurements.	EXEC UTE	Container Under Test	Container Under Test		F5, F7
2.3	Start the Energy Profiler	Start Energy Profiler	The Container Under Test starts the Energy Profiler.	EXEC UTE	Container Under Test	Energy Profiler		F4, F9
2.4	Execute the machine learning algorithm's training code	Train	The Container Under Test starts executing the training code from the Algorithm Driver and measuring Model metrics.	EXEC UTE	Container Under Test	Algorithm Driver		F8
2.5	Stop and collect Energy Metrics	Stop Energy Profiler	The Energy Profiler is stopped, and the energy metrics collected.	EXEC UTE	Container Under Test	Energy Profiler		F4, F9
2.6	Stop and collect time measurements	End measures	The time measurements are stopped, and the results collected.	EXEC UTE	Container Under Test	Container Under Test		F5, F7
2.7	Push metrics to Orchestrator	Push metrics	All metrics collected during training are sent to the Orchestrator.	EXEC UTE	Container Under Test	Orchestrator	IE2	F4, F5, F7
2.8	Send metrics to the KPI Handler	Send metrics	The Orchestrator sends the metrics to the KPI Handler.	EXEC UTE	Orchestrator	KPI Handler	IE2	F4, F5, F7

Figure 58. UML Sequence Diagram for the Infer Phase of the AI testing framework

Scenario								
Scenario name:		No. 3 – Start Infer						
Step No.	Event	Name of process/activity	Description of process/activity	Service	Information producer (actor)	Information receiver (actor)	Information Exchanged (IDs)	Requirement, R-IDs
3.1	Start the inference process	Start infer	The Orchestrator sends inference start action to the Container Under Test.	EXECUTE	Orchestrator	Container Under Test		F8
3.2	Begin time metrics collection	Start time measures	The Container Under Test starts time measurements.	EXECUTE	Container Under Test	Container Under Test		F5, F7
3.3	Start the Energy Profiler	Start Energy Profiler	The Container Under Test starts the Energy Profiler.	EXECUTE	Container Under Test	Energy Profiler		F4, F9
3.4	Execute the machine learning algorithm's inference code	Infer	The Container Under Test starts executing the inference code from the Algorithm Driver and measuring Model metrics.	EXECUTE	Container Under Test	Algorithm Driver		F8
3.5	Stop and collect Energy Metrics	Stop Energy Profiler	The Energy Profiler is stopped, and the energy metrics collected.	EXECUTE	Container Under Test	Energy Profiler		F4, F9
3.6	Stop and collect time measurements	End measures	The time measurements are stopped, and the results collected.	EXECUTE	Container Under Test	Container Under Test		F5, F7
3.7	Push metrics to Orchestrator	Push metrics	All metrics collected during inference are sent to the Orchestrator.	EXECUTE	Container Under Test	Orchestrator	IE2	F4, F5, F7
3.8	Send metrics to the KPI Handler	Send metrics	The Orchestrator sends the metrics to the KPI Handler.	EXECUTE	Orchestrator	KPI Handler	IE2	F4, F5, F7

7.1.3 Requirements

Requirements		
Categories ID	Category name for requirements	Category description
F	Functional Requirements	Reference features that are implementation agnostic and cover key functionalities.
I	Implementation Requirements	Reference to implementation details / needs linked with functional requirements
Requirement R-ID	Requirement name	Requirement description
F1	Multiple Algorithms	The framework should allow testing of several algorithms
F2	Multiple Datasets	The framework should allow several datasets to be used to test the algorithms
F2.1	Datasets for specific algorithm stages	The framework should allow datasets of a given type to individually support the multiple stages of testing an algorithm.
F3	Several target deployments	The framework should reflect the constraints of deploying algorithms in environments as the edge or the cloud
F4	Output Energy Metrics	The framework should compute metrics covering the energy consumption of all stages of the algorithms.
F5	Output Time Performance Metrics	The framework should compute metrics covering the time expenditure / consumption of all stages of the algorithms.
F6	Output Data Volume Performance Metrics	The framework should compute metrics covering the data volume of all stages of the algorithms.
F7	Output Model Performance Metrics	The framework should compute metrics covering the precision of models of the algorithms.
F8	Algorithm stages	The framework should map the relevant stages for algorithms including learning and testing a model.
F9	Energy profiler	The framework should provide the link with an Energy Profiler to enable collection of energy metrics.
I1	Energy Profiler using RAPL	The framework should adopt an energy profiler that is based on RAPL.
I2	Underlying support hardware - CPU	The underlying hardware where the framework is deployed must hold a CPU unit from a family that exports energy flags e.g., Intel Gen > 2; AMD > Zen 1.

I3	Underlying support hardware - GPU	The underlying hardware where the framework is deployed must hold a GPU unit from a family that exports energy flags e.g., NVIDIA.
I4	Container availability	The framework should adopt a container technology e.g., Docker to provide code portability and isolation for testing purposes.
I5	Container configurability	The container technology adopted by the framework should allow to emulate restrictions to the considered hardware.
I6	UNIX operating system	The framework should be deployed in a system adopting a UNIX operating system such as Linux (despite of the considered distribution).

8. Conclusion and next steps

There are two environments that allow comprehensive data management between the data provider and the data consumer, both deployed as cloud-based environments:

1. **Orchestration services environment:** It contains the tools and services necessary for the transformation and homogenisation of data received from local data sources and prepare them for publication in the Data Space, as well as the tools and services to transform the data received from the Data Space to the data structures used in local databases. Consequently, this environment is an intermediate phase that allows not only to publish data for consumption by one or more connectors of the Data Space, but also to consume data provided by the data space and transform it for local use. Therefore, it also contains the tools and services required by the different UCs to support the data transformation, tools and services like visualisation and interfaces, distributed analytic services and workflow management tools, Wrapper for security computations and sensitive data, etc.
2. **Data Space environment:** It contains the necessary tools and services to facilitate the search and identification of data published by other connectors and manage the transfer of said data between connectors. It also has tools to manage the security of the connections (DAPS server), the catalogue of available metadata, etc. which are mandatory in the framework of both IDSA and GAIA-X.

These cloud-based environments allow the Use Cases (and their sub-use cases) to select, transform, harmonise their data available and publish it at GREEN.DAT.AI data space. Furthermore, they ensure that the UCs can search, identify, obtain, and consume data from other data sources depending on the needs of existing tools and services as well as those developed and installed by WP3.

As also depicted in **Figure 1** (Section 1), the key results of WP2, achieved during the first half of the project, include:

- For data ingestion, the tools deployed is related to the environment in which they will be used, for orchestration services Kafka and local (custom) connectors and for Data Space service and the Sovity connector (based on an EDC connector)
- The StreamHandler and the Workflow Management Engine controls the tools and services required for harmonisation, storage, processing, reporting and visualisation of data, all integrated around the orchestration services and connected with local data bases.
- The analytic services include the energy Efficiency Testing Framework ingest data from the orchestration services or local data bases.
- For those case in which the analytic tools require data that are not available in orchestration services and/or local data bases, the data can be obtained using the data space services for data sharing (see first bullet).
- Visualisation tools have been designed, developed, tested, and deployed at pilot sites based on their use case requirements. Security aspects related to data, tools and orchestration services use are managed using KrakenD, IoT Trust-based IDs and Data & Execution protection.
- Orchestration services environment and related infrastructure used as an intermediary step to enable and facilitate data management between local data bases and GREEN.DAT.AI data space or the analytic services.

GREEN.DAT.AI environments ensure that the infrastructure is highly decentralised and focused on support new generation of tools and services in a computing continuum context, while improving the security and confidentiality of the data usage in local data bases, the orchestration environment, and the Data Space.

The deployment of tools and services resulting from WP3 tasks has started at selected pilot sites – as early adopters to facilitate the identification of hardware and software issues – which will lead in the next months to consolidate the demonstration capabilities of the pilot sites detailed in WP4.

8.1 Next steps

Continuous development and improvement are important activities for the tools and services required for the management of data processing environments; consequently, during the coming months the technical partners will continue testing and validating the tools and services in both environments based on the bugs reports they received from the pilots.

GREEN.DAT.AI Data Space includes the mandatory components to have a functional DS; therefore, and with the objective to improve its interoperability capabilities, GREEN.DAT.AI connectors will be tested and validated by interacting with “external-to-the-project” Data Spaces – those capable to provide fully operational DS environment in the framework of IDSA and GAIA-X.

Considering that Task T2.5 – Energy Benchmarking tool has implemented the base backend system and its integration with UC3 and UC4 with no major problems identified, during the next months (finishing in December 2024) it will continue with the UC integration, perform tests to evaluate the complete workflow and prepare the documentation.

Similarly, Task T2.6 - Integration of Demonstration Services will complete until December 2024 the deployment of the testing infrastructure to ensure that pilots’ UCs have fully tested and deployed the solutions required. Complete integration activities will be documented in the deliverable D2.2, due by M24.

9. References

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1. ANNEX I – Ethics Checklist

Ethics Checklist and Questionnaire

A. PERSONAL DATA

1. Has **personal data** going to be processed for the completion of this deliverable? **No**
2. Are “**special categories of personal data**” going to be processed for this deliverable? (whereby these include personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, and trade union membership, as well as, genetic data, biometric data, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation). **No**
3. Has the **consent** of the individuals concerned been acquired prior to the processing of their personal data? **N/A**
4. In the event of processing of personal data, is the processing:
 - obviously “**Fair and lawful**”, meaning executed in a fair manner and following consent of the individuals concerned or based on another - acknowledged as adequate and proportionate as per above - legal basis?
 - Performed for a **specific (project-related) cause** only?
 - Executed based on the principle of **proportionality and data minimisation** (meaning that only data that are necessary for the processing purposes are being processed and such deductive reasoning is documented)?
 - Based on **high-quality, updated, and precise** personal data?

N/A
5. Are there any provisions for a storage limitation period of the personal data-in case of storage- after which they must be erased? **N/A**
6. Are all **other lawful requirements** for the processing of the data (for example, **notification of the competent Data Protection Authority(s)** or undergoing a **DPIA procedure** and consulting with the competent DPA, if and where applicable) adhered to and on what legislative basis are such notifications justified as necessary or dismissed as unnecessary? **No**
7. Have individuals been **made aware of their rights** on the processing of the personal data as per the GDPR and the relevant and executive national legislation (particularly the rights to access, rectify and delete the personal data and their right to lodge a complaint with the relevant Competent Authority) and if yes, by what demonstrable means (e.g. the informed consent form as per above or as per other Templates, attached herein?) **N/A**
8. Even if anonymized or pseudonymized or aggregated data are referred to, does the dataset contain **data** that could potentially (even via the combined use of other datasets) **be traced back to individuals**? If yes, what specific measures are taken to ensure this data (i) is anonymized or pseudonymized and (ii) cannot be used to track individuals without their consent? If no, what is the scientific methodology used to collect and gather said data? **N/A**

9. In the context of risk assessment, prediction, and forecasting, as foreseen in the scope of the GREEN.DAT.AI project, **is there any risk** that personal data could be inadvertently revealed in the event of an **emergency** or **unusual event**, because of the dataset usage, either on its own or combined with other openly available datasets, triggering identification or unwanted disclosure of Personal Identifiable Information (PII)? What measures are in place to protect - still identifiable if the dataset allows such extraction - **personal data** in these circumstances? **No**
10. Is there any potentially PII in the datasets, **disclosable by combination with other datasets**, either open data or proprietary? If yes, how is PII adequately anonymized or pseudonymized or how other datasets that by combination may result in unwanted or illegal disclosures or identification before any processing takes place? **No**

B. DATA SECURITY

1. Have proportionate security measures been undertaken for protection of the data, considering project requirements and the nature of the data? **Yes**
 - If yes, brief description of such measures (including physical-world measures, if any)
Identity and Access Management tools have been deployed and are used in all environments used to manage data in the project.
 - If yes, is there a data breach notification policy in place within your organization (including an Incident Response Plan to such a breach)?
2. Given the **large-scale nature** of some datasets, are there specific measures in place to protect **included personal data** at scale at the data source or in the possession of data processors? **Yes**
3. Are there specific measures in place to secure **sensitive infrastructure data**, if present? **Yes**

C. DATA TRANSFERS

1. Are personal data transfers beyond project partners going to take place for this deliverable? **No**
2. Are personal data transfers to public authorities going to take place for this deliverable? **No**
3. Do any state authorities have direct or indirect access to personal data processed for this deliverable? **No**
4. Considering that the Project Coordinator is the “controller” of the processing and that all other project partners involved in this deliverable are “processors” within the same contexts, are there any other personal data processing roles further attributed to any third parties for this deliverable? And if any, are they conformed to the GDPR provisions? **No**
5. Given the geographical diversity of the datasets, are there measures in place to ensure compliance with specific personal data protection regulations **in different jurisdictions** i.e., at the place of the data source establishment as well as at the place of the establishment of a Data processor? **N/A**
6. Are there additional protocols for data transfers involving **sensitive infrastructure data** if present? **N/A**

D. ETHICS AND RELATED ISSUES

1. Are personal data of children going to be processed for this? **No**
2. Is **profiling** of identifiable individuals in any way enabled or facilitated for this deliverable? **No**
3. Are **automated decisions** for identifiable individuals made or enabled on the basis this deliverable? **No**
4. Have partners for this deliverable taken into consideration system architectures of **privacy by design** and/or **privacy by default**, as appropriate? **Yes**
5. Have partners for this deliverable taken into consideration gender equality policies or is there an explicit reasoning that dismisses such risk as unsubstantiated or such need as irrelevant as per the methodology of work and production of the deliverable? **N/A**
6. Have partners for this deliverable taken into consideration means of protecting the confidentiality of the dataset if it is not signified as open data? **Yes**
7. Are there additional considerations around the collection and processing of data **that could potentially be used to infer patterns about individuals**? **No**
8. Have partners identified any **additional ethical issues** related to the processing of sensitive infrastructure data? **N/A**
9. Is the Project considering the need for an all people-inclusive policy in the future within its overall goals and not only the “tech-savvy” (i.e., elderly people not familiar with some tech devices, poor people) and does it entail possible proposals for that? **N/A**

2. ANNEX II – StreamHandler Topics

Topics defined in StreamHandler per partner/organization

A. ITC

Topic	Description	Sample Messages
greendatai.itc.kontool.scheduled_requests	The topic where the ITC pilot data messages related to the scheduled requests, where the User can alter the stored output schema by changing the initial structure and/or adding static information, from the KONECTA tool data ingestion service are published.	<p>Sample #1</p> <pre>{ "id": "dea3a292-a769-42d8-86e6-f619c6fb6dba", "result": {"time_of_entry": "18042024T143612Z"} }</pre> <p>Sample #2</p> <pre>{ "id": "dea3a292-a769-42d8-86e6-f619c6fb6dba", "result": {"type": "ENTRY", "time": "18042024T143612Z"} }</pre>
greendatai.itc.kontool.events	The topic where the ITC pilot data messages related to the events, where User sets a logical comparison, i.e., smaller, or equal, larger, equal, unequal etc. for numbers, same or not the same for strings, from the KONECTA tool data ingestion service are published.	<pre>{ "id": "d4gha292-akl9-asd8-9le6-fl8t46fb61ca", "event_occured": true }</pre>
greendatai.itc.kontool.statistics	The topic where the ITC pilot data messages related to the statistics, where User chooses type of aggregate (min, max, average) and sets the frequency of the aggregate. This must have a lower frequency that the underlying requests. E.g., if request occurs every 5 minutes, average can be constructed every >5 minutes, from the KONECTA tool data ingestion service are published.	<pre>{ "id": "c0bcc713-0ced-4e28-9822-6180e872a531", "summary_type": "min", "frequency": 10, "result": 123 }</pre>

<p>greendatai.itc.kontool.forecasts</p>	<p>The topic where the ITC pilot data messages related to the created forecasts, where the User chooses to create forecasts, sets the forecasts frequency (which can't be lower than the underlying requests frequency) and the number of periods to forecast. It is assumed that each underlying request corresponds to a different period, i.e., if 10 requests have been made, these correspond to 10 realised periods, from the KONECTA tool data ingestion service are published.</p>	<pre>{ "id": "ad9e2a71-1b96-4cc7-adba-1e53c2f68381", "frequency": 5, "periods": 10, "result": ["<t+1 forecast>", ... , "<t+10 forecast>"] }</pre>
<p>greendatai.itc.um.parcels</p>	<p>The topic through which parcel geo entities will be streamed in form of standard geojson messages. UM will submit the parcels that require data processing through this topic. ML service workflow endpoint will then be notified with new parcels that need to be processed.</p> <p>Single message can contain one or many parcels as “features” is an array.</p>	<pre>{"type":"FeatureCollection","features":[{"type":"Feature","geometry":{"type":"Polygon","coordinates":[[[1795049.453786618,5882229.6847755825],[1795030.202840889,5882196.867540781],[1795029.0728170667,5882195.104379647],[1795022.7692355406,5882185.320755084],[1795430.6829980614,5881943.301756972],[1795460.2597219096,5881993.615971805],[1795052.7770181298,5882235.383605784],[1795049.453786618,5882229.6847755825]]]},"properties":{"fid":34,"Pid":4751912,"Name":"KRAČINA-HUSAR","Area":13045.2564},"crs":{"type":"name","properties":{"name":"urn:ogc:def:crs:EPSG::3857"}}}]}</pre>
<p>greendatai.itc.um.harvesting</p>	<p>The topic through which harvesting results that include the original parcels will be streamed as standard geojson messages. UM will submit the results from Scenario 1 – Harvesting optimization via this topic.</p> <p>Single message can contain one or many parcels as “features” is an array.</p>	<pre>{"type":"FeatureCollection","features":[{"type":"Feature","geometry":{"type":"Polygon","coordinates":[[[1795049.453786618,5882229.6847755825],[1795030.202840889,5882196.867540781],[1795029.0728170667,5882195.1043796465],[1795022.7692355406,5882185.320755083],[1795430.6829980614,5881943.301756972],[1795460.2597219096,5881993.615971805],[1795052.7770181296,5882235.383605784],[1795049.453786618,5882229.6847755825]]]},"style":{"fill":"#2f5f7c","color":"#2f5f7c","fill-opacity":0.5,"opacity":1.0,"weight":1.0},"properties":{"fid":34,"Pid":4751912,"Name":"KRAČINA-HUSAR","Area":13045.2564,"HarvestingDate":"2023-07-</pre>

		21T12:00:00.000000000Z"},"crs":{"type":"name","properties":{"name":"urn:ogc:def:crs:EPSG::3857"}}}}}
greendatai.itc.um.crophealth	<p>The topic through which crop health results that include the original parcels and coloring styles, will be streamed as standard geojson messages. UM will submit the results from Scenario 2 – Pest and disease detection via this topic.</p> <p>Single message can contain one or many parcels as “features” is an array.</p>	<pre>{ "type": "FeatureCollection", "features": [{ "type": "Feature", "geometry": { "type": "Polygon", "coordinates": [[[1795049.453786618, 5882229.6847755825], [1795030.202840889, 5882196.867540781], [1795029.0728170667, 5882195.104379647], [1795022.7692355406, 5882185.320755083], [1795430.6829980614, 5881943.301756972], [1795460.2597219096, 5881993.615971805], [1795052.7770181298, 5882235.383605784], [1795049.453786618, 5882229.6847755825]]] }, "style": { "fill": "#90ff00", "color": "#90ff00", "fill-opacity": 0.5, "opacity": 1.0, "weight": 1.0, "properties": { "fid": 34, "Pid": 4751912, "Name": "KRAČINA-HUSAR", "Area": 13045.2564, "Health": 0.543496253185494, "AnomalyFactor": 0.6195190846920013, "crs": { "type": "name", "properties": { "name": "urn:ogc:def:crs:EPSG::3857" } } } } }] }</pre>
greendatai.itc.um.fertilizationmaps	<p>The topic through which fertilization map results, including coloring styles, will be streamed as standard geojson messages. UM will submit the results from Scenario 3 – Fertilization map generation via this topic.</p> <p>Single message can contain one or many parcels as “features” is an array.</p>	<pre>{ "type": "FeatureCollection", "features": [{ "type": "Feature", "geometry": { "type": "Polygon", "coordinates": [[[1795108.578576177, 5882203.439274133], [1795086.460268928, 5882181.87795155], [1795086.0450440734, 5882152.7129747765], [1795107.5403334638, 5882130.5268396735], [1795136.6159371994, 5882130.110134448], [1795165.2760542245, 5882100.528534772], [1795179.8138044514, 5882100.320099607], [1795194.1437656614, 5882085.529279367], [1795223.219212979, 5882085.112290259], [1795230.5919981662, 5882092.299204099], [1795223.427049152, 5882099.694649187], [1795208.8893019154, 5882099.903156817], [1795201.7243283265, 5882107.298590783], [1795216.46991373, 5882121.672490154], [1795194.9749237234, 5882143.858867042], [1795180.4371022636, 5882144.067329351], [1795166.1070236606, 5882158.858226414], [1795151.5691761305, 5882159.066641411], [1795108.578576177, 5882203.439274133]]] } }] }</pre>

		<pre>133],[1795108.578576177,5882203.439274133]]]},"style":{"fill":"#00ff00","color":"#00ff00","fill-opacity":0.5,"opacity":1.0,"weight":1.0},"properties":{"fid":133,"mapUuid":"0bc70ba5-79dd-4636-938f-01cf55308726","zone":1,"attributes":{"area":0.3150651008605957,"rates":[50],"ratesHeaders":["NPK 27 0"],"ratesPrices":[0],"ratesUnits":["KG_HA"],"Pid":4751912,"Name":"KRAČINA-HUSAR","Area":13045.2564},"crs":{"type":"name","properties":{"name":"urn:ogc:def:crs:EPSG::3857"}}}}}</pre>
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B. WABOOST

Topic	Description	Sample Messages
greendatai.waboost.kontool.scheduled_requests	The topic where the WABOOST pilot data messages related to the scheduled requests, where the User can alter the stored output schema by changing the initial structure and/or adding static information, from the KONECTA tool data ingestion service are published.	<pre>{ "id": "dea3a292-a769-42d8-86e6-f619c6fb6dba", "result": {"time_of_entry": "18042024T143612Z"} }</pre> <p>Or</p> <pre>{ "id": "dea3a292-a769-42d8-86e6-f619c6fb6dba", "result": {"type": "ENTRY", "time": "18042024T143612Z"} }</pre>
greendatai.waboost.kontool.events	The topic where the WABOOST pilot data messages related to the events, where User sets a logical comparison, i.e., smaller, or equal, larger, equal, unequal etc. for numbers, same or not the same for	<pre>{ "id": "d4gha292-akl9-asd8-9le6-fl8t46fb61ca", "event_occured": true }</pre>

	strings, from the KONECTA tool data ingestion service are published.	
greendatai.waboost.kontool.statistics	The topic where the WABOOST pilot data messages related to the statistics, where User chooses type of aggregate (min, max, average) and sets the frequency of the aggregate. This must have a lower frequency than the underlying requests. E.g., if request occurs every 5 minutes, average can be constructed every >5 minutes, from the KONECTA tool data ingestion service are published.	{ "id": "c0bcc713-0ced-4e28-9822-6180e872a531", "summary_type": "min", "frequency": 10, "result": 123 }
greendatai.waboost.kontool.forecasts	The topic where the WABOOST pilot data messages related to the created forecasts, where the User chooses to create forecasts, sets the forecasts frequency (which can't be lower than the underlying requests frequency) and the number of periods to forecast. It is assumed that each underlying request corresponds to a different period, i.e., if 10 requests have been made, these correspond to 10 realised periods, from the KONECTA tool data ingestion service are published.	{ "id": "ad9e2a71-1b96-4cc7-adba-1e53c2f68381", "frequency": 5, "periods": 10, "result": ["<t+1 forecast>", ... , "<t+10 forecast>"] }
greendatai.waboost.um.location1-data	The topic where the new WABOOST stationary device pilot data will be submitted through. Data consists of JSON Array of device timeseries.	[{"Timestamp":"2024-06-12T11:00:00.000000000Z","Temperature":14.304859924316407,"Potential of Hydrogen":14.0,"Conductivity":679.0000000000001,"Dissolved Oxygen":7.709458817119399,"Total Dissolved Solids":18308.0,"Oxidation-Reduction Potential":0.0},{ "Timestamp":"2024-06-12T12:00:00.000000000Z","Temperature":14.399999999627472,"Potential of Hydrogen":14.0,"Conductivity":679.0000000002328,"Diso

		lved Oxygen":7.717740298429101,"Total Dissolved Solids":18648.0,"Oxidation-Reduction Potential":0.0},...]
greendatai.waboost.um.location1-events	<p>The topic where detected events will be submitted from the Scenario 1 - Monitoring.</p> <p>Data consists of JSON Array of detected event timeseries.</p>	<pre>[{ "Timestamp": "2023-08-20T00:00:00.000000000Z", "Event Type": "Heatwave" }, { "Timestamp": "2023-08-21T00:00:00.000000000Z", "Event Type": "Heatwave" } ...]</pre>
greendatai.waboost.um.location1-predictions	<p>The topic where detected events will be submitted from the Scenario 2 - Water parameters predictions.</p> <p>Data consists of JSON Array of prediction timeseries. Message is the same as in “greendatai.waboost.um.location1-data” topic</p>	<pre>[{"Timestamp":"2024-06-12T11:00:00.000000000Z","Temperature":14.304859924316407,"Potential of Hydrogen":14.0,"Conductivity":679.0000000000001,"Dissolved Oxygen":7.709458817119399,"Total Dissolved Solids":18308.0,"Oxidation-Reduction Potential":0.0},{"Timestamp":"2024-06-12T12:00:00.000000000Z","Temperature":14.399999999627472,"Potential of Hydrogen":14.0,"Conductivity":679.0000000002328,"Dissolved Oxygen":7.717740298429101,"Total Dissolved Solids":18648.0,"Oxidation-Reduction Potential":0.0},...]</pre>

C. SERVEO

Topic	Description	Sample Messages
greendatai.serveo.uprc.automl_data	The topic, which is the input to the “ST3.2.2 - Algorithm Selection & Hyperparameter Tuning/AutoML” service.	<pre>{ "TripId": 26836882, "StartTime": 2021-01-01T00:15:50.000000000Z, "EndTime": 2021-01-01T00:39:58.000000000Z, "StartStationId": 506, "EndStationId": 95.0 }</pre>
greendatai.serveo.uprc.automl_bikedemand	The topic related to the bike demand forecasting from “ST3.2.2 - Algorithm Selection & Hyperparameter Tuning/AutoML” service.	
greendatai.serveo.kontool.tucTasks	The topic where KON’s tool sends TUC’s tool (Accelerated Processing Engine) a message and keywords to search for in it.	<pre>{ "id": "str", "keywords_label": "str", "message": "str" }</pre>